

ReNEW

D4.7 - LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional
Synchro-modality City Logistics Hub v2

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
4SHIP	4Shipping
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
APDL	Administração dos Portos do Douro
CC	Command Centre
CCNR	Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine
CEMT	Confederation of European Maritime Technology Societies
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DGRM	Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services
DT	Digital Twin
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HPC	High Performance Computing
IMEC	Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum
ING	Internationale Nederlanden Groep
ITA	Instituto Tecnológico De Aragon
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KNT	Konnecta
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MAG	Magellan
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides
OHB	Opleidingscentrum Voor Hout En Bouw Vzw
PAN	Panteia
RIS	River Information System
ROC	Remote Operation Centre
UGAL	Universitatea Dunarea De Jos Din Galati
VHF	Very High Frequency
WP	Work Package
ZES	Zero Emission Services

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable outlines Living Lab 1's efforts to enhance resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport through innovative solutions, including the development of a Smart Terminal and Floating Modular Platform, integration of sensor technologies, and real-life demonstrations to test various aspects of the project.

The introduction section of the report provides a comprehensive examination of the impact of climate change on weather patterns in Europe, focusing particularly on Belgium and Ghent. Within Ghent, water management plays a crucial role in maintaining stability and safety.

To address the impact of climate events on logistics operations, Living Lab 1 in Ghent focuses on implementing synchromodal solutions and improving energy resilience. Challenges include aligning project objectives with city aspirations and integrating green technologies into infrastructure.

The outcomes of the Ghent Living Lab contribute to the project's impact objectives and are shared with other cities to optimize inland waterway utilization.

An overview of the existing infrastructure of LL1 is presented, focusing on digital and hardware infrastructure, physical infrastructure, remote control shipping, and data collection.

KPIs of LL1 include ensuring navigability for inland waterways during extreme weather events, enhancing resilience of land and sea infrastructure, achieving a 20% increase in modal shift, ensuring smooth passenger and freight transport, and reducing environmental impact.

Partners involved, i.e. OHB, SF, UGAL, IMEC, KNT, ICCS, Akkodis, ITA, and Sintef Ocean contribute with their expertise remote operation, ship design, digital infrastructure, sensor deployment, drone systems, scenario development.

Use Case 1 of the Ghent Living Lab focuses on developing a "Smart Terminal" to enhance resilience in urban logistics, which include the Smart Terminal itself, Smart Ships, propulsion systems, remote-controlled sailing, mooring systems, loading/unloading systems, drones for aerial reconnaissance, and a Mobile Command Centre for crisis management.

Use Case 2 within the Ghent Living Lab focuses on the design and demonstration of a Floating Modular Platform (FMP) for emergency transport and power supply during crises. The FMP is envisioned as a flexible and adaptable floating platform featuring an urban battery, automated mooring systems, ramps, and other essential components. It aims to provide support during floods, dry periods, and potential disease outbreaks.

Use Case 3 focuses on the implementation of an Environmental Alert System within the Ghent Living Lab, aimed at monitoring and optimizing the resilience of inland waterway transport (IWT) through

IoT technology and sensor installations. This initiative enhances Ghent's synchromodality and infrastructure resilience, particularly during crisis situations such as fluctuating water levels.

Use Case 4 focuses on the implementation of a Floating Energy System, comprising two primary aspects: the utilization of batteries for propulsion and the deployment of batteries for providing off-grid power supply infrastructure.

OHB, along with partners, will conduct real-life demonstrations to test various aspects of the project, including response to flooding scenarios, resilience of command centers during disasters, development of autonomous platooning capabilities, and testing of GALILEO positioning systems and floating power systems for emergency situations.

As concluding remark, Living Lab 1 focuses on enhancing resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport through innovative solutions, including the development of a Smart Terminal, Floating Modular Platform, and integration of sensor technologies.

According to implementation plan, initial testing has been completed, with further development planned, aiming to address key scenarios such as staff loss mitigation, infrastructure resilience assessment, and smart terminal operations visualization.

1 Introduction

1.1 LL High Level Implementation Plan & Preparation

The LL 1 serves as the core demonstration platform for important aspects of Green Resilient Inland Water Transport (IWT). LL 1 focuses on specific objectives aligned with the overall goals of the ReNEW project. Implementation plans for LL 1 is developed using a multidisciplinary approach, incorporating expertise from Automation, Computer Programming, Mechanical Engineering, Naval Architecture, et.al. The proposed iterative approach contributes to refine strategies and solutions throughout the development process based on input from various sources, including stakeholders and project partners. Tools like Innovatrix (presented in D4.6) aid in the mapping of needs process, provides updates information into how each LL contributes to achieving project objectives.

Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchronomodality Resilient City Logistics Hub

The Living Lab at Ghent (LL1) aims to create a flexible and resilient logistics system for multi-user and multifunctional purposes. The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate change on the operations of the City Logistics Hub.

Location

City Logistics Hubs in the city of Ghent - sea canal (between Ghent (B) and Terneuzen (Netherlands), canals, rivers, canals with tidal action with a wide range of infrastructure.

Corridor / Area

Belgium to Netherlands

Figure 1: Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchronomodality Resilient City Logistics Hub (<https://renew-waterways.eu/>)

1.2 Mapping the ReNEW Output

In the following is given an overview of the deliverable in the project.

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D4.7 LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub v1
Final Design and Implementation plans.

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
T4.3 LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub	<p>The Living Lab focuses on the impact of events caused by climate changes on the operations of the City Logistics Hub.</p> <p>(a) Implement Syncro-modality Solutions for Cities based on Infrastructure for Cargo Loading, to improve resilience and sustainability. The City Logistics Hubs will synchronize the arrival of the freight over barges with various transport modes that are compatible with the objectives of the City of Ghent to focus on quality of living and environmental sustainability. Solutions tested will include cargo bikes and electrical vehicles, that can move freight and people into and out of the city. Study the infrastructural setups and enhancements to support automated cargo loading.</p> <p>(b) Improve energy resilience with Power solutions innovations, including batteries</p>	<p>The document provides an overall description of the Living Lab and the four use cases defined in it. Chapter 2, defines the use cases which address the definition of the LL demonstration requirements and specifications. Chapter 3 specifies the performance of the Simulation Scenarios in the context of the living lab.</p>

2 LL1 - Ghent's Multifunctional Synchronomodality City Logistics Hub

2.1 Context-Introduction-Key initiatives

In **D4.6. Initial Design and Implementation Plan** we have provided an overview of the impact of climate changes on the weather in Europe and more specifically in Belgium.

In this section we delve deeper into the findings of the impact of climate changes during the past year 2023.

The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)¹ declared 2023 as the warmest year on record, with a global average temperature surpassing the previous record set in 2016. The increase in temperatures was attributed to escalating concentrations of greenhouse gases and weather phenomena like La Niña and El Niño. The average temperature for the year was recorded at 14.98 degrees Celsius, with a notable increase of 1.48 degrees Celsius compared to the pre-industrial period. Every day in 2023 was at least one degree Celsius warmer than pre-industrial levels, with almost half the year experiencing temperatures at least 1.5 degrees Celsius higher. November 17 and 18 marked a peak, with temperatures exceeding 2 degrees Celsius warmer, unprecedented in records.

The high air temperatures were explained by the unusually high surface temperatures in the ocean, caused by rising concentrations of greenhouse gases reaching the highest levels ever measured in the atmosphere in 2023.

In Europe, 2023 was the second-warmest year, with temperatures above average for 11 months and September being the warmest on record. Heavy precipitation triggered significant flood events across the continent throughout the year, with notable storms and flooding occurring in various countries. The increasing frequency and severity of such events pose significant threats, as seen in past floodings, leading to fatalities, displacement of populations, and economic losses.

The European Commission has taken action, as outlined in the Recommendation for the 2040 emissions reduction target, in response to these challenges².

¹ <https://climate.copernicus.eu/global-climate-highlights-2023#:~:text=2023%20marks%20the%20first%20time,than%20%2C%20B0C%20warmer.>

² Recommendation for 2040 emissions reduction target (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_24_588)

Local Situation in LL1

As outlined in the M12 Implementation Plan, Ghent has formulated a vision statement regarding water utilization within and surrounding the city. This report focuses exclusively on the economic aspect, specifically the use of water for transportation purposes.

The water level in Ghent is regulated by various lock complexes, which keeps the water level fairly stable. The city center of Ghent has a fine-meshed network of small waterways that enter the center from outside the urban area. In the northern part of Ghent there are more rectilinear canals and docks in the port area. The network of waterways is connected by the curvi-linear Ringvaart canal as a central carrier for both shipping movements and for buffering water. The water level, and therefore also the city center of Ghent, is protected against water peaks and strong fluctuations by locks that control the water around the city.

As a result, Ghent's territory is divided into three distinct water areas:

1. The Northern area (from Ringvaart Noord to Evergem lock, North Sea Port canal from Ghent to Terneuzen, and Portus Ganda) maintains a normal water level of 4.45 meters TAW³.
2. The southern area (from Ringvaart between Evergem and Merelbeke, Kuip van Gent, above the Scheldt, Leie, to Ghent Canal to Ostend) operates with a water level of 5.61 meters TAW.
3. The southeastern basin extends from the tidal Scheldt to Gentbrugge and the lock complex of Merelbeke.

Over the years, seven lock complexes have been constructed between these three water basins to regulate water levels: Brusselsepoort sluis, Sint Jorissluis, Tolhuissluis, Scaldissluis, Gentbruggesluis, sluizencomplex Evergem, and sluizencomplex Merelbeke (Figure 2).

In addition to these lock complexes, the city center of Ghent is further protected by additional infrastructure, including two floodgates with single doors and a lock that is selectively closed during high water levels to shield the city center from potential flooding.

Thanks to this extensive system, which has evolved over centuries (Figure 3), Ghent's city center has remained largely immune to flooding and damage for decades.

Following our annual tradition, De Vlaamse Waterweg nv conducts a comprehensive inspection and cleaning of the Ghent inland waterways. To facilitate work below the waterline, temporarily the water level is lowered by 50 cm between November 13 and 23. The precise control over this process, enabled by locks, ensures that the water level will return to normal afterward.

³ Definition of TAW: The Second General Water Passing (TAW) is the reference height against which height measurements are expressed in Belgium. A TAW height of 0 meters is equal to the average sea level at low tide in Ostend, which was measured between 1878 and 1885 with the gauge in the Handelsdok.

Figure 2: Overview locks system to control the water level in Ghent

Specifically, our lock and weir operators will lower the water level of the Lieve, the Leie, the Ketelvaart, the Muinkschelde, and the Upper Scheldt. This involves closing the weir where new water flows in and keeping the weir where water flows out open. Once the desired water level is achieved, both weirs will be closed. The water level will begin to decrease on Friday morning, November 13, and return to normal starting from November 20.

Figure 3: Overview water tides rivers in Ghent

The vision statement of the city of Ghent regarding water management also emphasizes the need to "increase the sponge effect" within the city. It is concluded that simply preserving existing water spaces is insufficient. Flanders continues to experience increasing urbanization and hardening. Simulations conducted by the University of Leuven predict a doubling of paving in Flanders from 10% to 20% by 2050. Consequently, rainwater has fewer opportunities to infiltrate the subsurface and flows off more quickly, thereby increasing the risk of flooding in downstream areas. Creating additional space for water is therefore necessary to enhance Ghent's robustness and safety, particularly in anticipation of the expected effects of climate change.

There are clear signals that climate change will result in more frequent and intense sudden rain showers, leading to localized flooding. This is particularly evident during summer thunderstorms. Convective thunderstorms are typically very localized yet highly intense. If they occur over urbanized areas, the consequences can be severe.

2.1.1 Test Conditions in LL1

As evident from the description of water management techniques applied in Ghent, strict control is maintained over the water level. However, this does not necessarily create a comparable situation to the devastating flood experienced in Pepinster on 26th July 2021, where excessive rainfall resulted in a powerful current, claiming 39 lives and damaging 10,000 houses. Additionally, the opening of the dam on the Vesdre River, releasing 150 m³ of water per second, turned the river into a destructive torrent that swept away everything in its path.

In response to this, our team sought information about a port directly exposed to the sea, where influences such as intense winds, high waves, and strong currents could be simulated to closely resemble a flood scenario. While such conditions are present in North Sea harbours, detailed information was lacking.

Fortunately, we identified a reference area with remarkably similar characteristics in Hamburg, where discussions with the Hamburg Port Authority yielded valuable information and historical data.

Based on this collaboration, we worked with naval architects from UGAL and the responsible shipyard to design a basic model of the ReNEW vessel. However, meetings with naval and marine specialists at the Hamburg Port Authority revealed that the current design of the Green Wave, being a flat-bottomed zero-emission vessel, was unsuitable for the ReNEW rescue use cases.

Here are some of the observations made during these discussions:

- Very strong currents and strong winds at certain times of the year,
- Low structure of the gangway of the Green Wave vessel type,
- The 70-kW engine's inadequacy to navigate against strong currents,
- Significant wave action caused by ferry ships,
- The necessity for sufficient battery capacity to power the engines.

Below, in Figures 4 – 6, are examples of information obtained regarding currents, wind, water levels, etc.

Figure 4: Flow velocity in m/s

Also, long term data are available about the wind force in meter per second and the direction of the wind. That is valuable information concerning the creation of waves which will slow down the vessel.

Figure 5: Arithmetic mean of the high tide levels or low tide levels of a specific period under consideration.

We also have insight in the extreme weather conditions in that area:

Figure 6: Number of storm flood in Hamburg from 1951 to 2013⁴

2.1.2 Vision and Challenge to be Addressed in ReNEW

The Living Lab 1 Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchronodal city Logistics Hub will focus on the impact of events caused by climate changes on the operations of the City Logistics Hub.

(a) Implement Syncro-modality Solutions for Cities based on Infrastructure for Cargo Loading, to improve resilience and sustainability. The City Logistics Hubs will synchronize the arrival of the freight over barges with various transport modes that are compatible with the objectives of the City of Ghent to focus on quality of living and environmental sustainability. Solutions tested will include cargo bikes

⁴ MThw / MTnw (Arithmetischer Mittelwert der Tidehochwasserstände bzw. Tideniedrigwasserstände eines bestimmten betrachteten Zeitraums.) MThw / MTnw is the Arithmetic mean of the tidal high-water levels or tidal low water levels of a specific period under consideration.

MThb = (Mittlerer Tidehub Arithmetischer Mittelwert der Tidehübe eines bestimmten betrachteten Zeitraums)
MThb: Mean tidal range Arithmetic mean of the tidal ranges of a specific period under consideration

and electrical vehicles, that can move freight and people into and out of the city. Study the infrastructural setups and enhancements to support automated cargo loading.

(b) Improve energy resilience with Power solutions innovations, including floating Batteries. Test Ship and Shore digital twin solutions for autonomous mooring and loading.

Challenges in the testbed Ghent

One of the challenges was fitting the Ghent logistics hub into the aspirations of the city of Ghent, as stated in their vision statement. This was drawn up in collaboration with the water authority, De Vlaamse Waterweg, and includes various sub-areas, such as economy on the water, shared water use for transport and recreation. We have thoroughly addressed this matter in the M12 Design & Implementation Plan.

From our perspective, we strive to align the project objectives and the baseline of the policy makers' vision.

To this end, integrating some of the emerging green technologies with advanced, original resilience-assist infrastructure, based on increased autonomy, is required.

Particularly,

- i) autonomous low or zero-emission barges,
- ii) use of floating platforms, for better manoeuvrable characteristics, platooning capability and emergency power supply capabilities,
- iii) several means of transportation of the cargo and people in case of disaster and iv) a shore module with an MCC, including a movable automation control centre, new automated mooring system and a floating pontoon with a modular land ramp are the main solutions to be delivered, to satisfy the scope of the project, as regards the Ghent LL.

As we develop the LL objectives, our intention is to subsequently disseminate them to other cities, which are essential for optimizing the utilization of inland waterways.

Moreover, the outcomes of the Ghent Living Lab contribute to fulfilling the impact objectives established within the project. The five shared LL value indicators utilized for the project's Living Labs, presented in Table 2 are applied.

Table 2: Overview Living Labs Common Value Indicators (also presented in deliverable D.46)

Impact	LL1 Gent	LL2 Duero	LL3 Netherlands	LL4 GENT Duisport	LL4 Danube
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	80%	80%	30-50%		
Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	90%	95%	80%		
20% increase in modal shift	20%	20%	10%	20%+	20%+
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	√	√	√	√	
Reduce environmental impact [CO ₂ e]	90%	10%	10%	90%	10%

2.2 Existing Infrastructure & Tools

2.2.1 Existing Digital and Hardware Infrastructure

Only one urban vessel of OHB operates remotely by SF and the second is on the loop, the corresponding digital infrastructure already exists. The autonomous ship sends the information to the Shore control centre in Antwerp from SF. LiDAR cameras and some sensors are already installed on the remote-controlled ship, but more are definitely needed, as explained in the M12 report.

The utilization of AIS facilitates ship localization, with consideration given to the installation of em-trak equipment. The em-trak AIS transceivers are being evaluated due to their promise of optimal performance, reliability, connectivity, and value. This is achieved through continual and extensive advancement in core technology and product development spanning two decades. Such efforts ensure the provision of AIS transceivers with unparalleled performance, reliability, and connectivity.

Research into the utilization of a 5G private network in collaboration with the provider Proximus is ongoing. This private network offers users complete control over its access. We intend to conduct tests with this 5G network towards the end of 2024. The 5G network proves highly adept for managing ships and drones autonomously from a shore command center, ensuring safety and reliability.

2.2.2 Existing Physical Infrastructure

The Smart Terminal

The Smart Terminal is an ecosystem in which the terminal consists of various components, such as terrain, ship, loading and unloading infrastructure and storage options. A modular system has been developed based on the idea of developing the terminal operations in such a way that they can continue to operate in the event of staff loss.

The system encompasses diverse functionalities, including remote-controlled sailing, autonomous mooring, and remote loading and unloading facilitated by a remotely operated crane. These components are further elaborated upon in the use cases.

The infrastructure comprises not only the physical structures but also the terrain and its configuration.

The site used as a test base in the project is the subject of an extensive study in which a surveyor was first appointed to take the necessary measurements. The site has an elongated shape and is located on a lost part of the North Sea Port, close to the busiest lock in Belgium, the Westbekesluis.

Location of the site in the port of North Sea Port

In Figure 7 is given the location of the terrain in the North Sea Port region. In figures 8-10 one may see the location near sea canal and distribution of the various blocks for construction and exploitation of the site.

Figure 7: Location of the terrain in the North Sea Port region

Figure 8: View from the waterside

Figure 9: Location near the seacanal of North Sea Port Ghent

The surveyor measured the site and made a profile of the site with a view to its construction in 4 phases.

Figure 10: Distribution of the various blocks for construction and exploitation of the site

The elongated shape of the site has the advantage that 400 meters of quay are available so that several ships can moor at the same time. The site is also close to various arterial roads to the city and inland via the ring road around Ghent, R4. Furthermore, it is located at the junction of the connection of waterways, canals, the Scheldt River and the NSP sea canal.

The site profile inclines towards the quay and requires excavation (Figure 11).

The architect has devised the fundamental layout of the site to optimize loading capacity by utilizing the entire length of the quay. This design also facilitates efficient entry of trucks from one side and their departure from the other side of the site.

Figure 12: Overview of the various components for exploitation

Furthermore, reinforced concrete slabs are provided (15 m x 15 m) where a 100 ton crane can be set up to conduct loading and unloading activities from ship to truck and vice versa. In Figure 12 are presented the components for the exploitation while in Figure 13 are given details of the locations for loading on the Terminal.

Figure 13: Detail of the locations for loading on the Terminal

2.2.3 Remote Control Shipping

The existing physical infrastructure of LL1 is rather simple. OHB already owns 2 urban barges, while one is under construction. Moreover, there is an onshore command centre by SF to operate remotely the vessels. This remote-control center is located in Antwerp and is far from the location where the vessel is sailing. This distance is considered for the critical scenario of the Living Lab 1 where the control of the vessel should be transferred to a safe location. On the shoreside OHB collaborates with local logistic providers and has quays and infrastructure in the testbed Ghent.

One of the key elements in remote operation, is the situational awareness. This awareness is provided through the cameras onboard the vessel. We also investigated the use of cameras to control the Smart Terminal and the various components, such as the mobile crane. We have done some lab tests on specific industrial cameras which are waterproof, and we will install these cameras onboard the vessel and the crane. Testing of the existing hardware for object recognition is essential for secure operations of remote-controlled shipping. Object detection is a technique used for finding the vessels and objects on the way of the ego-vessel to detect the probable collisions. It also highlights the objects for the remote captains who are sailing from the control centre, so they vividly see the objects on the way of the vessel.

Figure 14: SF cameras installed on the urban test vessel

The subsequent phase involves outfitting the urban barge for remote control from a significant distance, operated from SF's shore control center in Antwerp.

The shore control centre from SF in Antwerp is fully equipped with technical installations that can visualize the data from the vessel. Once the control system is designed and installed onboard the vessel, it will connect to the equipment on board a ship using a PLC connection to receive data. This data will then be transferred to the cloud and visualized to the remote captain at the remote operation center. Therefore, he can control the ship remotely. In the bridge ashore there is an experienced captain who will steer the ship remotely.

Figure 15: Shore Control Center of SF - Foto : De Standaard 16 april 2023

2.3 Data Collection

The use cases in the Living Lab require different types of data.

- Environmental data, collected through sensors in the seaport and canal in Ghent and Zelzate, is arguably the most important, as it directly relates to the concepts of resilience and sustainability.
- Additionally, data about the availability and location of ships is required, which is provided by AIS data.
- Information about the location and operation of cranes (whether on land or on a ship) can be transmitted if it is possible to apply a track and trace device to the crane.
- The data on the floating battery is the same as that of the ship.
- The Energy Management System (EMS) could provide information about the status of the battery systems, as well as potential management of the systems regarding charging capacity.

2.3.1 KPIs

Below is a concise overview of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the M12 report, with detailed discussions provided subsequently. The summarized KPIs can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: Ghent LL Impacts and Target KPIs (presented also in previous deliverable, D.4.6)

Impacts	Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	20% increase in modal shift	Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	Reduce environmental impact [CO2e]
LL1 Ghent	80%	90%	20%	✓	90%

- **Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50 % capacity during extreme weather events – 80%**
 - o An application scenario will be developed by ITA (see further in the report).
- **Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions – 90%**
 - o We aim to enhance the resilience of both land and sea infrastructure against extreme weather conditions and man-made events. While these structures themselves are robust, the human factor required to operate them must be carefully managed and monitored as it can be the weak link prone to failure. Given the extensive automation planned for various parts of the infrastructure, our objective is to ensure at least 80% capacity at the network level during disruptions.
- **20% increase of modal shift**
 - o Despite the fact that the site is under investigation and has not yet been constructed, we have already carried out tests with transshipment of a 1,350 T ship onto trucks and on the quay. Stakeholder meetings were held with various building materials traders and a comparative study of the common orders.

The orders from the FMCG ((Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG), also known as consumer-packaged goods (CPG), are products that are sold quickly and at a relatively low cost) were collected and submitted in 1 order for the Ghent Living Lab to the plaster products manufacturer KNAUF, located in the south of the country.

These goods were loaded onto the ship and sailed to Ghent. An agreement was made on site with the various traders to use their own trucks to collect the cargo in accordance with their order. This way, 300 T were unloaded from the ship in one go, instead of every trader driving back and forth to Enghis to pick up his orders. In this way, 15 fur truck movements were avoided.

Figure 16: Unloading MP75 pallets in view of the modal shift subtask

-
- **Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport**
 - To achieve resilient and flexible transport of people and goods in an urban environment, good cooperation is needed between the regulatory authorities that are responsible for loading and unloading points on the land side.
 - There must also be strong collaboration with the water authority to ensure the maintenance of waterways and associated infrastructure such as quays, mooring facilities, and so forth.
 - Furthermore, there must also be a sufficient supply of goods and people within the urban area.

- **Reduce environmental impact (CO₂ and Nox) – 90%**
 - o In the urban vessel, we will implement electric propulsion with e-engines and battery packs, thereby achieving a 100% reduction in emissions of CO₂, NO_x, and other pollutants typically emitted by internal combustion engines.

2.3.2 Partners and their role

OHB, as the owner of urban barges, participates in designing the Floating Modular Platform (FMP) and coordinate its implementation, working closely with SF and UGAL. SF a well-known remote operator of automated and semi-autonomous vessels in Belgium, provides the remote-control technologies, from onshore control centres, and expertise for increased resilience. They support the LL with commercial services and impact pathways. SF installs their equipment and remotely navigate the vessel from the headquarters in Antwerp. The captain will have in front of him 6 monitors showing the live camera streams, one monitor for the monitoring dashboard showing vessel speed, and network condition, one monitor for the navigational map, and one for the list of events and alarms. In this project, SF is also investigating the remote operation of the crane. The knowledge built on remote control of the vessels will be used to provide a solution for cranes. UGAL's research team designs and validates the pontoon and support construction and operational activities regarding FMP. IMEC and KNT focus on developing digital infrastructures, including local digital twins and data spaces, while providing operational knowledge. ICCS will utilize in-situ sensors and satellite altimetry data to estimate deployment of rescue equipment in disaster areas. Akkodis assists in developing a drone system for mapping disaster areas and providing data to the command center. ITA works on application scenarios and set up KPIs for Living Lab use cases using digital twins and simulation models. Sintef Ocean advises on the development of remote-controlled or automated mooring systems, drawing from their experience with similar systems for ferries and short sea ships.

2.4 Use cases

Methodology

We employ the Design Thinking Methodology to develop various use cases. Design Thinking is a problem-solving approach that emphasizes understanding and addressing the genuine needs of users to generate effective solutions.

Figure 17: Design thinking methodology (presented in D4.6)

The design thinking methodology follows five steps as shown in the figure above and was mentioned in D4.6, M12.

Design Thinking includes several steps which are divided into three main phases:

- (a) the *Understand* phase, which includes *Empathize* and *Define* steps,
- (b) the *Explore* phase which includes the *Ideate*, and *Prototype* steps, and the,
- (c) *Materialize* phase which includes the *Test* and *Implement* steps.

2.4.1 Use case 1: Smart Terminal

The work conducted within Use Case 1 focuses on designing and constructing a "Smart Terminal" to enhance resilience. The primary goal of the Smart Terminal is to establish a remote-controlled connection between an autonomous barge and the shore, while also developing a (Mobile) Command Center for crisis management scenarios. Use Case 1 comprises distinct components that are developed independently and later integrated to form a cohesive and resilient system:

2.4.1.1 Smart Terminal

The "Smart Terminal" comprises a collection of "intelligent" components that integrate to create a cohesive system:

- ✓ Remote-controlled ships, managed from the Command Center (CC), for mooring and positioning.
- ✓ Urban vessels equipped with a remote-controlled loading and unloading system that is mobile and can be maneuvered on and off the ship.
- ✓ Utilization of a remotely controlled drone for conducting inspections in hazardous areas without direct human intervention.

2.4.1.2 Smart Ship

In this phase of the project, at M18, the plan has been finalized based on calculations by the naval architect, utilizing the previously studied flat-bottomed ship design by UGAL. Data provided by the HPA was instrumental in enhancing both the hydrodynamic and structural performance of the barge, leading to the proposal of a new project and subsequent construction. This new designed vessel is intended to be adaptable for use in various regions of the European inland waterway network, such as certain sectors of the Lower Danube or Hamburg Port Area. Following analyses of simulations, tables, and statistics provided by the HPA, the original design underwent a comprehensive revision. To improve the ship's stability, it was decided to construct a vessel measuring 20 meters in length and 4.5 meters in width (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Design of the new hull

Figure 19: Cutting of the aluminum plates according to the drawings

Figure 20: Welding of the aluminium plates for the hull

In Figure 19 and Figure 20 are presented images from construction stages within the shipyard. The progress made on this process is proceeding as planned:

- The ship design has been tailored to accommodate turbulent waters with strong currents and high waves.
- The plan has been translated into a cutting plan for the aluminum plates.
- The aluminum plates have been cut accordingly.
- Welding work has commenced.
- Motorization has been developed in collaboration with engineers, and the engines have been ordered.
- The next steps involve the development of the electrical package.
- Significant attention will be devoted to designing a customized battery pack that meets the requirements for current, sailing range, and power needs for external applications.

Provisional specifications of the new vessel:

Below are the initial specifications outlining the key dimensions and characteristics of the upcoming vessel:

- Length overall = 19.7 m
- Beam = 4.3 m
- Depth = 2.15 m
- Draft 0.4 -> Displacement = 8.45 m³
- Draft 0.5 -> Displacement = 13.4 m³
- Draft 0.8 -> Displacement = 34.4 m³ (full load)

2.4.1.3 Propulsion

In the initial design iteration, we explored the possibility of employing outboard engines, driven by the necessity for increased engine power to navigate against strong currents. The following table outlines the various propulsion configurations investigated:

Table 4: Propulsion configurations

Version	Propulsion	Bow thruster	Stern thruster
1	2 Outboard engines inside hull	Outboard	-
2	2 Outboard engines inside transom	Inboard	Inboard
3	2 Outboard engines on transom + inboard engine	Inboard	Inboard
4	2 inboard engines	Inboard	Inboard

The 3D model of different versions of the vessel are given in figures 21-24, respectively:

Figure 21: Propulsion set up configuration 1 (2 out board engines mounted in the hull)

We also explored alternative applications of the outboard engines and different configurations.

Figure 22: Propulsion set up configuration 2 (2 outboard engines mounted in the transom)

Figure 23: Propulsion set up configuration 3 (2 out board engines mounted outside of transom, 1 inboard engine, at center-plane)

In collaboration with the naval architect, we deliberated on various options and concluded that utilizing outboard engines is not advisable due to the ship's predominant operation in shallow waters. The potential risk of damage to the propellers and rudder system is significant. Hence, we have determined that employing robust inboard motors may offer a viable solution (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Propulsion set up configuration 1 (2 inboard engines)

Given the ship's intended automation in shipping operations, manoeuvrability is of utmost importance. As part of this strategy, we utilize bow and stern thrusters connected to the PLC for remote control takeover.

2.4.1.4 Remote controlled sailing

The automation of the new AVATAR vessel which is under construction will be done by SF. The vessel building will be completed in September 2024. To automate the urban barge, different sensors and devices are required. Some cameras are already selected and some other are under research. As shown in Figure 25 part (C), the sensors and required devices will be installed onboard the vessel.

Figure 25: Automated vessel sailing methodology

In addition to the sensors, a control system of SF is required to provide the communication with the sensors and navigational instrument onboard. SF is currently designing the control system adaptable to the new AVATAR barge. Another important aspect of automation is proper interfacing. The interfaces will be developed between the equipment onboard and SF control system. There are ongoing discussions for the implementation of the suitable interfaces to enable correct control of the thrusters, and other elements.

Another important part in automation of the vessel is the remote-control station as shown in part (A) in the figure. SF will utilize one of their control stations for the new urban barge in ReNEW project. There might be some modifications required specifically on the camera views or the control methodology from the remote operation center. This will be investigated during the tests after the installation of control system onboard the new urban barge.

One important element to be developed is the ability to dock the vessel from remote control center. For this purpose, a number of sensors such as suitable cameras are being tested and investigated. Once the devices are selected and the barge building is completed, the devices will be installed onboard the barge. To enable transfer of this data to the remote operation center, the network

connectivity is required as shown in part (B) in the figure. Different network equipment is under research. The most suitable network equipment will be selected to be installed onboard. The network topology will be designed as well to provide safe communication link between the vessel and remote operation center.

2.4.1.5 Remote Controlled Mooring – Station Keeping

In this part of the smart terminal, we will develop a remote-controlled mooring system for the urban ships. The ships will be equipped with bow and stern thrusters, in addition to the normal propulsion line, so that they are able to remain in "station" mode waiting to dock with other vessels or at the quay.

2.4.1.6 Remote Controlled Loading and Unloading System

We have opted for a flexible and resilient loading and unloading system for use from the ship instead of on the water. A multi-user and multifunctional loading and unloading system has been selected (Figure 26).

TECHNICAL DATA BM 214

Dimensions L/W/H	2430/1950/1925 mm
max. lift capacity	to 2100 kg
Engine power	Diesel, 25,3 kW (34,4 PS)
max. lifting height	2850 mm
Dead weight (w/o arms)	starts at 1485 kg

Figure 26: Lift truck model Palfinger

This model of remote operating lift truck is an existing model of the Palfinger group mainly used for road, which needs some adaptations to operate from a vessel. In the upcoming months, we will collaborate with the manufacturer and SF to assess the necessary adaptations required for remote operation from the MCC.

The current model available is diesel-powered, which may not be suitable for use on a zero-emission urban vessel. We are conducting further investigations to determine the feasibility of acquiring this model in an electric version.

SF, IMEC and OHB will examine how the control of the machines (crane, drone and loading platform) can be taken over from the remote-control operating system that comes with the machines to the cloud for the web-based application, so that the captain in the CC can control the and management can take over.

SF is designing an architecture for the automation of a mobile crane which will be selected by OHB considering a proper movement for getting on and off the urban barge. Once the mobile crane is selected, SF will investigate the possible interfaces and complete the design of the system architecture to automate the mobile crane and enable the remote operation of the crane from the control system. The timely implementation of the system is dependent on the timely selection and availability of mobile crane.

So far, the activities on mobile crane include the study of the cranes and the possible methodology of collecting information to provide situational awareness for the remote captain. Furthermore, a preliminary design is done for the required elements and network connectivity. There are ongoing discussions between OHB and SF for the required interfaces and soon the technical team of SF will discuss the parameters and interfaces with a possible crane company.

2.4.1.7 Drone as “eyes in the sky”.

In this project, Living Lab 1 is centred around creating a flexible and resilient logistic system for multi-user and multifunctional purposes. This Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate change on the operations of the City Logistics Hub. To achieve this, the AKKODIS team works in collaboration with SF and OHB to identify drone requirements and perform benchmarking on drone companies.

Our objective in this project is to devise a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for the drone LL1 aims to implement on its barges.

As stated in the Grant Agreement the mission drone is as follows: “Using the drone on board one of the ships allows visual reconnaissance to enhance steering”.

Through our exchanges with LL1, we identified two missions for the drone:

- “Help navigate the barge by detecting obstacles in the waterway when visibility is uncertain.”
- “Assist with searching for human life in case of disaster.”

In this sense, we needed to define a series of minimum requirements when choosing the Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). Thus, defining the parameters would later help us find the best option available on the market.

The requirements defined and agreed with the rest of the partners involved in the project are the following:

1. Hardware:

- **Range:** 1km range minimum (no maximum, the more the better).
- **Autonomy:** 15/20 minutes minimum per flight / around 1 hour maximum.
- **Frequency:** 1 use per week minimum (maximum unknown).
- **Heights:** Minimum and maximum unknown.
- **Weight:** Capable of transporting multiple cameras (standard, infrared, and night vision).
- **Recharge:** Induction recharge, but possibility for battery switch.
- **Shelter station:** Induction charge compatibility, and protection from bad weather (rain, snow, humidity).
- **Weather:** Able to fly in bad weather (rain, wind, humidity).

2. Software:

- Return home.
- Video feedback.
- 4G/5G Compatibility.

3. Out of scope:

- Remote control of the drone directly from the RCC.

With everything clarified, we embarked on a market search for a product that would fulfil most, if not all, of the agreed-upon requirements. After evaluating options from various brands across different countries, it was determined that, for this project where the drone is not the primary focus but rather a complement to the main solution proposed by the ReNEW project, robustness and coherence are essential criteria. In this regard, DJI and its Matrice 30T⁵ product appear to be the most suitable choice. Table 5 presents a summary of our comprehensive research, including specification comparisons and market surveys.

The Matrice 30T drone emerges as the prime selection for the Renew project, featuring advanced technical specifications, an impressive 1 km communication range, and a flight autonomy of 15-20 minutes. Its robust design guarantees dependable performance, even in challenging weather conditions, while the autonomous recharge capability enhances operational efficiency.

⁵ DJI, <https://enterprise.dji.com/>

Moreover, the Matrice 30T appears to be the most suitable for ReNEW strengthened by its seamless integration with DJI's FlightHub 2 software, streamlining drone management, optimizing mission planning, and facilitating real-time monitoring.

This harmonious combination ensures a streamlined and effective approach to aerial mission management.

Table 5: Comparative table and matching with the requirements of the different market options

Requirements	Matrice 30T	Mavic 3T	Mavic 3 PRO	Autel EVO II	Yuneec H520E	Skydio X10	Skydio X2E
Range	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Autonomy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Frequency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Dimensions	470x585x215mm	347x283x107mm	347x290x107mm	457x558x108mm	551x482x309mm	79x65x14.5cm	66x56x20cm
Max Altitude	5000 – 7000 m	6000 m	6000 m	7000 m	???	4572 m	3657.6 m
Weight	3780 g	1050 g	958 g (No thermal cam)	1150 g	1860 g	2110 g	1325 g
Recharge	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shelter station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Weather	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Return to home	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Connectivity	Research in progress						
Price (Only the drone)	10 506 €	7 214 €	3 499 €	6 133 €	5 035 €	???	???

However, there is a budgetary limitation for drone acquisition that needs to be taken into consideration in this project. This drives us to continue checking the market and continue to explore in search of the best possible option to carry out the mission successfully.

2.4.1.8 Multifunctional Transport Box

A multifunctional transport box will facilitate loading and unloading in a semi-autonomous operation. Various designs have been drawn up for this purpose, but the study continues even further due to new insights into the materials to be transported.

The first designs have been made and will be submitted to operational stakeholders in the summer of 2024 to verify the usability in real economic life.

2.4.1.9 Mobile Command Centre

Within work package 3, the ReNEW consortium partners are working towards the development of a first digital twin demonstrator in which navigability of the waterways can be assessed and KPI's related to the sustainability (and later resilience) of transport modes can be monitored. Based on scoping workshops and interactions between LL1 and WP3, Work Package 3 included following user stories into its first demonstrator concept that match with the Living Lab 1 requirements (see also D3.2):

- As an administrator I want to have basic user management so only people with the right login can access the app
- As a user I want to have a map overview of the Ghent area with basic map controls (zoom, pan, 3D-toggle, street names, search)
- As a user I want to view information on the height of the water level
- As a user I want to view the vessels carbon footprint
- As user I want to view bridges critical clearance
- As user I want to view a heat map of fairway channel depth
- As user I want to be warned about the occurring disruption (infrastructure, accident, etc).

The initial demonstrator will gradually expand in its capabilities. If accurate information on the waterways near the Ghent area are available, assessments can be made on e.g. the navigability of the FMP and the Smart ship in the designated area, provided the Digital twin disposes of detailed information on the parameters affecting this navigability in the designated area (river information). Comparisons could be made in terms of sustainability and later in terms of resilience KPI's, where the uptime and effectiveness of these vessels under extreme weather events are compared to existing vessels. Afterwards, more scenarios and parameters can be considered.

In order to achieve situational awareness of the multimodal city logistics hub through the Mobile Command Centre, (real-time) data sources providing information on the physical assets of the hub (smart ship, remote controlled loading and unloading system, drone, FMP, the environmental alert system, the floating energy system) need to be made digitally available for being connected onto the ReNEW Data Space - created by Konnecta - that feeds the Digital Twin with data. In Figure 27 are given the dataspace components and the local digital twin, mentioned in D4.6 also).

Figure 27: Dataspace components and the local digital twin. The graph depicts also the interlinks of the digital tools with the various data sources and models.

2.4.2 Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform

Result of the M12 report (in brief)

Within Ghent Living Lab, the design and demonstration of a Floating Modular Platform (FMP) is aimed for emergency transport and power supply during crises. The FMP, a floating modular platform, features an urban battery, automated mooring systems, ramps, et.al., intended for use during floods, dry periods, and potentially disease outbreaks. The FMP has as building blocks the existing barges, own by OHB as well as the new vessel. Collaboration between UGAL, OHB, and SF aims to implement a smart navigation system and automate the ramp and mooring systems.

Naval Architecture involves hydrostatic, stability, and hydrodynamic simulations using CFD codes for ship resistance, propulsion, and manoeuvrability and these activities are developed by UGAL based on input from partners.

Extensive numerical testing with existing vessels precedes FMP development. Hydrostatic and stability calculations for the urban barge assess the ship's stability across different load conditions. CFD studies estimates resistance, pressure distribution, and power predictions for different FMP configurations. Results show the capability to transport passengers and cargo safely.

LL1, by means of demonstrating the functionality of FMP aims to enhance resilience through a flexible floating platform with multiple functionalities, benefiting residents, public services, logistic providers, and crane operators.

Design of a new type of vessel based on the new challenges.

One of the primary objectives in considering a new barge design was to facilitate its utilization by various inland stakeholders in Europe, thereby contributing to enhanced transportation, economic efficiency, and sustainability.

The new vessel, designed and constructed with consideration for inputs characteristic of other sectors of the European inland waterway network, can be utilized in extreme situations in other regions. The vessel's design and propulsion take into account the improvement of seakeeping performance, considering that inland waters (other than the Ghent-Terneuzen Canal) may experience significant wave heights ranging from 0.6 to 1 meter. Consequently, the new vessel could also be used on certain sectors of the Danube. A potential use of the innovative vessel could be in port of Hamburg (identified as having similar conditions with Ghent, described in paragraph 2.1.2), where areas with restricted channels and restricted air drafts may not be available for larger vessels.

Regarding the shallow water conditions, in port areas, especially those situated at the end of the estuary, the minimum depth is approximately 2 meters (during pronounced tides, some ships may encounter problems). The air-draft is a concern, influenced by strong tides, the rise of the Elbe's water level due to floods leading to low bridge clearance (see Figure 28). Regarding seakeeping considerations, the significant wave height in the port is approximately 0.6 meters, with direct influence on ship motions. The ship design implied besides ship resistance, manoeuvrability and propulsion, investigation on seakeeping performance for various significant wave heights.

The new concept can easily manoeuvre through such constrained spaces, providing access to areas that might be off-limits for larger ships, facilitating efficient loading and unloading operations. The vessel is suitable for transporting specialized cargo, such as bulk goods, construction materials, or goods that require direct access to the shoreline. This type of barge can offer a more tailored solution for specific types of cargo handling within the port.

Another important aspect the use of this concept can support local industry by facilitating the transportation of goods to and from specific areas within the port. This can be particularly important for industries with unique transportation needs.

Figure 28: Example of low bridge clearance, port of Hamburg, January 2023, (<https://hydroonline.hpanet.de/bridge/map>)

Another region where the new vessel could operate is within the Danube River basin, which has varying water depths, and there are sections with shallow areas. For instance, the Lower Danube (km 931 to km 100, Black Sea) has many sectors with excessive sedimentation. The design of the new barge, featuring a reduced draft, enables navigation through shallow sections, ensuring access to water areas that might pose challenges for larger vessels. The Danube River passes through multiple countries, and its tributaries and branches reach into various inland areas. New designed barge can navigate, not only the main river, but also the narrower tributaries, and branches providing access to remote and less accessible regions for transportation of goods (Danube Delta).

Also, the Danube have infrastructure limitations in certain areas, such as bridges and locks. The shallow water barge is more adaptable to these constraints, allowing for easier navigation through narrower channels and under lower bridges at the same time contributing to an enhanced intermodal connectivity. This enables seamless transfer of goods between waterways, roads, and rail networks, optimizing the logistics chain and supporting a well-connected transportation system.

In the figures 29 and 30, bathymetric measurements within Chilia arm/branch are given, showing the shallow navigation fairway, with lower depths of 0.8 meters. Chilia is one of three main distributary channels of the river Danube that contribute to forming the Danube Delta. Lying at the northernmost area of the delta, the distributary creates a natural border between Romania and Ukraine.

Figure 29: Bathymetric maps, Chilia branch (with permission of Administratia Fluviala Dunarea de Jos of Galati, Romania)

Figure 30: Bathymetric maps, Cernavoda bridge, Danube river (with permission of Marine Research Ltd. Romania)

The new design of the inland vessel has been proposed by partner OHB, considering the feedback from stakeholders in the ReNEW project and aligning with European standards and regulations. While the advantages of existing urban barges have already been demonstrated, the new design is also in compliance with DIRECTIVE (EU) 2016/1629 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 14 September 2016. This directive establishes technical requirements for inland waterway vessels, amending Directive 2009/100/EC and repealing Directive 2006/87/EC. According to Article 2 Scope of application, paragraph (a), this directive applies to vessels with a length (L) of 20 meters or more.

In accordance with Directive EU 2016/1629 and the standards applicable to all EU flags and types of inland ships, including ES-TRIN 2023/1, which became legally binding through a delegated act of the EU and a resolution of the CCNR (Central Commission for Navigation on the Rhine) and came into

effect on January 1, 2024, the new design represents a compact and comprehensive solution for potential beneficiaries in Europe and other regions.

The considerations during the design and construction phase are grounded in European policies and measures aimed at protecting inland waters and promoting the sustainability of inland waterway transport. These initiatives are European programs such as the European Green Deal, Agenda 2030, Fit to 55, Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Water Framework Directive, et.al.

During various technical meetings between OHB and UGAL, discussions revolved around key features such as dimensions, hull form, hull arrangement, propulsion, manoeuvrability, operational conditions, etc.

Various configurations of new design were proposed and discussed. Preliminary studies have been conducted with the aim of investigating the feasibility in terms of length, loading capacity, material, and weight of the ship, as well as the cost of the materials used.

The next table presents the main characteristics of the investigated designed versions:

Table 6: Main characteristics of the new vessel

Ship length [m]	15	20	25	30
Weight [t] - aluminium	6.6*	8.4	10.2	12
Immersion (TPc) [t/cm]	~0.5	~0.7	~0.9	~1.1
Displacement [t] for T=0.8 [m]	27.5	40.98	53.72	66.47
Cargo load [t]	19.4	30.5	41.0	51.5

For these versions a set of computations were performed in order estimate the hydrostatic performance, which are listed in tables A3.1, A3.2. and A3.3 presented in Annex 2 of the present report.

Figures 31, 32, and 33 depict the hydrostatic diagrams for three barge versions with lengths over all (LOA) of 20, 25, and 30 meters, respectively.

Figure 32: Hydrostatic diagram, LOA 25 meters

The Floating Modular Platform (FMP) case is investigated and going to be demonstrated within the Ghent LL. The FMP, as a whole configuration, is considered as a floating pontoon, possibly interacting with the 2 or 3 barges of OHB, when needed.

The design and validation of the FMP requires hydrostatic, hydrodynamic, and structural computation. This computation is executed with the use of an HPC and dedicated software, by UGAL. Some initial results of the CFD simulations are shown in figures 34 and 35 (reported in D2.1 in M12, also mentioned in D4.6, first version of implementation plan) with focus on pressure distribution on the hull, free-surface prediction, flow configurations, flow wake, separation, and vortices formation, in the scope of understanding and enhancing the hydrodynamic performance of the urban barge.

Figure 33: Hydrostatic diagram, LOA 30 meters

Figure 34: CFD simulations for the FMP

Figure 35: Different contours from the CFD simulations of the FMP

Figure 36 illustrates the investigated configurations of FMP having as building block the urban barges used in hydrodynamic numerical simulation, without the new designed vessel, as it was reported in M12. The computation of FMP including the new barge are to be reported in M24, in D.2.2.

Figure 36: Urban Barge configuration in the simulation cases.

The next table summarizes the various simulation cases performed in the hydrodynamic investigation. Altogether, there are a total of 156 computed cases.

Table 7: Simulation cases for LL1

A summary for the simulation cases performed.

Simulation Cases								
Urban Barge Speed [km/h]	Urban Barge in Deep water				Shallow Water Effect			
	UB	2 UB SBS	2 UB C	3 UB C	h/T = 1.2	h/T = 1.5	h/T = 2.0	h/T = 3.0
7	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑
8	☑	☑	☑	☑	☒	☒	☒	☒
9	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑
10	☑	☑	☑	☑	☒	☒	☒	☒
11	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑
12	☑	☑	☑	☑	☒	☒	☒	☒
13	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑
14	☑	☑	☑	☑	☒	☒	☒	☒

☑ performed ☒ not performed

where:

- h -water depth,
- T - draught of the urban barge,
- UB - urban barge,
- SBS - side by side,
- UB C - Urban Barges in convoy.

2.4.3 Use case 3: Environmental Alert System

Impact of the use of the urban vessel on the environment

ICCS utilize existing sensor technologies to provide an IoT component for monitoring and optimization of IWT resilience as part of the Digital Twin capabilities and support Living Lab 1. Therefore, in the framework of LL1, ICCS will install sensors for environmental data gathering upgrading the physical infrastructure and improving Ghent’s synchronomodality. The new sensors will provide a support ‘package’ for time of crisis (e.g. low/high water levels) increasing the overall infrastructure’s resilience.

Specifically, ICCS will install one piezoresistive pressure transmitter sensor for water level monitoring in 'Everstein' location, close to the main part of the Ghent's port (51.1041 N, 3.7250 E). In Figure 37: this location is depicted with the number 1. Also, in the second point at the Zelzate marina in the cross border with the Netherlands, a sonde consists of four different water quality sensors and one piezoresistive pressure transmitter sensor will be installed (51.2085 N, 3.8053 E).

Figure 37: The two locations for the installation of water level and water quality sensors.

At the Zelzate marina, a sensor box is already installed in the framework of Socorro European 2 Seas project (Interreg 2 Seas - SOCORRO – Ghent University (ugent.be)), as illustrated in Figure 38.

Thus, we could use their electricity connection without need installation of new solar panel. The sonde of sensors will be installed at a pole of approximately 3 meters height, which will be close to the marina and inside the water. The Aqua TROLL 500 is a five-port multiparameter sonde, including four sensor ports and a wiper port. The four water quality sensors which will be installed are: Temperature/Conductivity, Turbidity, Chlorophyll-a, and Dissolved Oxygen contributing to the environmental and ecological impact monitoring of inland transportation in the water ways of Ghent and further. The Aqua TROLL 500 is a fully customizable multiparameter sonde with interchangeable sensor that deliver accurate data and enable simplified calibration, panoramic data and report creation. This flexible instrument is ideal for spot checking and continuous remote monitoring when used with data services. Thus, this state-of-the-art sonde simplify data collection with equipment designed to be reliable, cost effective and easy to use. Also, this in-situ equipment is designed to withstand use in the harshest environments. Features designed to prevent breakage or failure

including: interlocking sensors for greater stability, titanium restrictor, fully potted sensors, redundant SD card storage, and multi-chamber design. Moreover, it consists of a mini calibration cup that uses only 50 ml of solution for calibration, reducing calibration cost by 5x over traditional methods. There are three different output options: RS485/MODBUS, SDI-12, and Bluetooth, while its maximum reading rate is 1 reading every 2 seconds. For the needs of the project, the output option of RS-485/MODBUS is going to be used. It operates in temperatures between -5° and 50° C, while its weight is around 1 kg. Furthermore, based on the technical documentation, this sonde is able to provide temperature measurements with accuracy $\pm 0.1^{\circ}$ C, dissolved oxygen with ± 0.1 mg/L, turbidity with $\pm 2\%$ of reading, and Chlorophyll-a with ± 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Figure 38: The sensor box installed in Zelzate marina in the framework of Socorro project.

Also, the piezoresistive pressure transmitter PR-36XW KELLER, which will be used for the water level monitoring, is a state-of-the-art sensor providing highly accurate measurements. This sensor has a digital interface RS485, which supports the MODBUS-RTU communication protocol for process values and configuration. It's a high-quality pressure transducer and tried-and-tested mathematical compensation with robust stainless-steel housing. The accuracy is $\pm 0,05$ %FS, while the maximum deviation within the temperature range (0-50 $^{\circ}$ C) is $\pm 0,1$ %FS.

In both locations, a HD33M-MB.2 Delta Ohm datalogger equipped with a GSM/GPRS module will be used allowing several physical quantities to be monitored remotely. In the framework ReNEW project, the version with input for standard RS485 MODBUS-RTU sensors will be used. Also, thanks to GSM/GPRS transmission, we will not have to remove the datalogger from its position or visit the two

locations, where the dataloggers are going to be installed, to download the data measured with the PC. The datalogger stores the measurements in the internal memory and transmits the acquired data via FTP, via e-mail or to an HTTP server (Cloud). Also, we could make a direct GPRS TCP/IP connection with a remote PC. The datalogger functions can be remotely controlled by sending SMS messages. For each detected quantity, we can set two alarm thresholds (high and low threshold), the alarm hysteresis and a delay in the generation of the alarm. The overrun of the thresholds can be signalled by alarm emails or SMS messages. The datalogger operates with 7 up to 30 Vdc power supply voltage. However, in 'Everstein' location, the datalogger will be powered by a solar panel of 10 W, which are going to be installed in the pole, as it is shown in the following picture (Figure 39). The datalogger is equipped with a switched power supply to output the sensors only when the measurement has to be carried out. It operates between -20° and +70 °C with LCD, and between -40° and +70 °C without LCD, while its weight is approximately 1 kg. Its dimensions are: 122 x 120 x 56 mm excluding the antenna.

Figure 39: Pole in 'Everstein' location, where the datalogger and the solar panel will be installed.

Water level measurements will increase the infrastructure's resilience of Ghent, but also will be used for the evaluation/validation of space-based altimetry observations which is a challenging task due to the limited access to historical gauge data. As inland water bodies play a key role in the global hydrological cycle, there is need for a homogeneous continuing monitoring system. However, the network of in situ gauges for the retrieval of water level heights is sparse, and in some cases the scientific community faces restricted access to historical gauge data. In this context, satellite altimetry measurements of inland water surface elevation are an important data source to supplement the limited river in situ gauge measurements. However, it is still very challenging to obtain accurate water level measurements over narrow rivers and canals. The sensors installed in the framework of LL1 will enrich the water level gauge network of North-West Europe.

Thus, in-situ network will leverage state-of-the-art sensing technologies to enable accurate water level monitoring with high temporal resolution whilst also facilitating remote data transfer. As it can be seen in Figure 40: 40, in-situ data contribute to the extraction of information about the dynamics of inland water levels. It can be achieved almost in real-time. The following image comes from a DEMO of another Horizon Europe project, in which ICCS installed in-situ sensors for inland water level monitoring in Athens, Greece.

Figure 40: Water level monitoring of Kifissos River in Athens, Greece with in-situ sensor

2.4.4 Use case 4: Floating Energy System

The study of use case four can be decomposed to the two following parts:

- i) use of batteries for the propulsion of the urban vessel and
- ii) use of the batteries installed on the vessels, so as the platform can operate as a giant power supply infrastructure.

For the propulsion the barges will be sailing using the power of the electric system combined with an extended battery system. The batteries to be installed on the existing vessels and the one developed, will provide an alternative source of power for propulsion, for a long range. They may be installed either “inside” the barge or on the deck, on top of the barge be installed in, for ex. in the transportbox.

Fig. 39 Floating battery concept

This platform can be used as a huge power supply for cascading effects, the battery will be exploited as floating off-grid power supplier (to a hospital or crisis center for example).

The use of large battery systems for emergency situations is an overarching goal.

The most actively involved parties are the public grid network operators, private constructors with need for energy-as-a-service, emergency units and grid back-up systems.

This study has just been completed. We have already done some tests with a test setup for this purpose. The final elaboration will be carried out over the next 12 months.

2.4.5 Implementation Plan: Key Milestones and Timeline

ICCS planned to install water level sensors during the winter months, specifically between December 2023 and January 2024, followed by the installation of water quality sensors. ICCS is working to a scoping review paper for the inland water level monitoring by satellites observations, which will be published until November of 2023.

The Table 8 and Figure 41 provides a comprehensive outline of the step-by-step implementation plan which is aligned with the plan template provided in D4.1 about the method of implementation of the living lab. Figure 8 delineates the activities involved in the implementation plan, while Figure 41 illustrates the GANTT Chart depicting the timeline and sequence of these activities.

Table 8: Activities of implementation plan of LL1

	Activities of implementation plan of LL1	Start Month	End Month
A1	Overall Implementation Plan Development	1	3
A2	<i>Use case 1: Smart Terminal</i>	1	3
A3	<i>Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform</i>	1	3
A4	<i>Use case 3: Environmental Alert System</i>	1	3
A5	<i>Use case 4: Floating Energy System</i>	1	3
A6	Design and Plan Specific Tasks	4	22
A7	<i>Use case 1: Smart Terminal</i>	4	16
A8	Close the analysis for the Smart Terminal	4	20
A9	Define the transport box design	4	20
A10	Select mobile crane or loading system for the ship	4	20
A11	<i>Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform</i>	4	18
A12	Define with UGAL and shipyard the final construction plan for the hull of the vessel	4	17
A13	Define with SF and UGAL the propulsion system for the vessel	4	16
A14	<i>Use case 3: Environmental Alert System</i>	4	18
A15	Finalise the environmental study and define sensors by Sintef	4	18
A16	<i>Use case 4: Floating Energy System</i>	4	22
A17	Finalise the study of the battery pack and EMS for the "floating Energy" use case	4	22
A18	Execute LL Construction Plan	12	24
A19	<i>Use case 1: Smart Terminal</i>	12	24
A20	Purchase of material and construct Transport box	12	24
A21	Implement crane or loading system for the ship	12	24
A22	Finalising the construction of the smart vessel and start testing remote control with SF	12	20
A23	<i>Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform</i>	4	22
A24	Purchase of material for vessel (alu, engine, spare parts)	4	20
A25	Purchase and configure mobile loading system	15	22
A26	<i>Use case 3: Environmental Alert System</i>	12	24
A27	Purchase sensors for the environmental system by ICCS	12	24
A28	<i>Use case 4: Floating Energy System</i>	12	24
A29	Purchase battery packs and software. Start engineering energy system	9	24
A30	Plan LL Operations	15	24
A31	<i>Use case 1: Smart Terminal</i>	15	24
A32	<i>Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform</i>	15	24
A33	<i>Use case 3: Environmental Alert System</i>	15	24
A34	<i>Use case 4: Floating Energy System</i>	15	24
A35	Monitor LL Operations	18	32
A36	<i>Use case 1: Smart Terminal</i>	18	32
A37	<i>Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform</i>	18	32
A38	<i>Use case 3: Environmental Alert System</i>	18	32
A39	<i>Use case 4: Floating Energy System</i>	18	32
A40	Implementation Assessment	32	36
A41	Assessment Report	32	36

Figure 41: Implementation Plan

3 Application Scenarios

The project is a research and innovation initiative that seeks to promote resilience and sustainability in inland waterway transport. Together with the LL1 partners and ITA and INL and VLTN application scenarios will be designed as described in the proposal.

1. Staff Loss Mitigation operations.

When the staff working in a terminal is disabled due to an external calamity or a pandemic, the system or procedure developed by ITA must switch the work to a level of automation so that the Smart terminal as a whole can continue to function. The personnel of a terminal (logistics manager, operator of the crane or loading installation, terminal operator, warehouseman, skipper, sailor, etc.) can fail in this scenario, jeopardizing the functioning of the terminal operations. Within Renew project we aim to find an answer to this by automating the operation of a terminal to a high degree. Furthermore, the scenario can be tested under conditions of varying degrees of personnel loss, such as 10%, 20%. The time element within which a switchover from human-driven actions is taken over by machine-driven actions is an important factor in this.

2. Infrastructure Resilience Assessment

The impact of the consequences of climate change has increased significantly in recent years. There are examples of this every month in Europe with far-reaching consequences for the population, infrastructure, and society. Examples such as the great flood in Belgium in Pepinster on July 19, 2021, May 19 in Italy in the Emilia-Romagna region and on May 24, 2023 in Spain (Regions of Valencia, Murcia and Andalucia) have a terrible impact on society with a lot of dead, homeless and human suffering. Setting up an analysis model of the different responses to climate disasters may limit the impact of these phenomena.

3. Smart Terminal Operations Visualization.

IMEC has developed concepts for visualizing the Smart Terminal's operations, incorporating various elements such as ship position, environmental data, ramp size, and crane positioning during loading and unloading. This animated visualization provides a comprehensive overview of the Smart Terminal's functions, serving as a valuable tool for all stakeholders (Figures 42 and 42). Additionally, it can be utilized for educational purposes, offering insights for policymakers and rescue personnel.

Figure 42: Render of a visualisation of the data from the ship

Figure 43: Data to retrieve from the vessel

3.1 Simulation scenarios of smart terminal

As outlined in D4.6, addressing the impact of staff loss on the Smart Terminal through simulation is an important step in ensuring its resilience during unforeseen events. The goal is to enhance the Smart Terminal's operational capabilities, allowing it to function seamlessly even when personnel are incapacitated due to external factors.

During the initial phase, a series of tasks were accomplished. Firstly, meetings with stakeholders were conducted to define the scope and objectives of the use case. These interactions not only provided clarity on available data and relevant information but also identified potential users of the tool.

Secondly, a thorough review of existing technology was undertaken to determine the most suitable platform for developing a virtual model of the Smart Terminal. Various simulation software and Business Process Modeling tools were explored, leading to the selection of Discrete Event Simulation (DES) technology. DES, known for its effectiveness in analyzing processes involving discrete, well-defined events, has broad applications across industries such as manufacturing, healthcare, logistics, and telecommunications. Its capacity to focus on the order and timing of events within a system makes it an invaluable tool for optimizing processes, identifying bottlenecks, and assessing system performance under several what-if scenarios.

Following this, the initial conceptual design of the Smart Terminal model has been developed.

Future activities have been outlined for the upcoming period, including:

- Organizing dynamic sessions with use case stakeholders to discuss the initial conceptual design of the Smart Terminal and gather additional information relevant to the model.
- Continuing the development of the simulation model based on feedback received from stakeholders.
- Introducing what-if scenarios and identifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the outcomes of different simulations.
- Validating and calibrating the model based on results obtained and feedback from users.
- Conducting final scenarios and presenting comprehensive results.

3.2 Real Life Demonstrations

Real life demonstrations will be held by OHB with SF, UGAL and other partners.

1. **Demonstration with several rescue urban boats from OHB** which will set up a rescue scenario. In this demonstration, the response to flooding in a densely populated urban area will be tested to assess the rapid deployment of rescue operations for both people and goods.
2. **Resilience of the Command Center:** The impact of a disaster, such as floods or fires, on the logistic infrastructure can be assessed by relocating the web-based interface, along with the data stream connection with the Smart Terminal, from the onshore Command Center to an alternative Command Center.
3. **Develop autonomous platooning capability:** Demonstration of the impact of road obstruction involves utilizing urban vessels in a platooning mode, wherein one scenario employs a physical connection and the other utilizes a digital connection by SF with two remote-controlled vessels. This FMP configuration has the capacity to rescue passengers and transport a substantial quantity of goods.
4. **Demonstration of solutions where water obstruction** can block the waterway.
5. **The testing of the effectiveness of the GALILEO positioning system** in managing the vessels from the onshore Command Centre. Switch from GPS and GALILEO will prove the resilience in the communication channels and systems between ships and CC.
6. **Test the readiness of the floating power system** to provide power in emergency situations when the grid fails and essential installations require power. This floating power system is an elaboration of a flexibly resilient grid power installation that can be used anywhere within the range of the vessels.

4 Conclusions

The Living Lab 1 Belgium, in the ReNEW project, is a research and innovation laboratory with real life application scenarios that will prove resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport (IWT).

The Living Lab 1 in Ghent focuses on assessing the impact of climate change events on the City Logistics Hub and implementing syncro-modality solutions to improve resilience and sustainability, aligning with the city's objectives. Challenges include integrating the hub with Ghent's vision and aligning project objectives with policymakers' vision by integrating emerging green technologies with advanced infrastructure. The outcomes contribute to fulfilling project impact objectives, with intentions to disseminate them to other cities for inland waterway optimization.

In Use Case 1, the objective is to design and construct a "Smart Terminal" to enhance resilience. The Smart Terminal facilitates the connection between an autonomous barge and the shore in a remote-controlled manner and includes the development of a (Mobile) Command Center for crisis situations. The Smart Terminal comprises several intelligent components:

- ✓ Remote-controlled ships managed from the Command Center for mooring and positioning.
- ✓ Urban vessel equipped with a remote-controlled loading and unloading system that is mobile and can be driven on and off the ship.
- ✓ Use of a remotely controlled drone for inspections in hazardous areas without direct human intervention.

In Use case 2, the Floating Modular Platform (FMP) that integrates features such as an urban battery, automated mooring systems, ramps, and more was approached. UGAL, OHB, and SF collaborate to implement a smart navigation system and automate ramp and mooring systems.

Designed for versatility, the FMP serves during floods, dry periods, and potential disease outbreaks. Prior to its development, extensive numerical testing, including hydrostatic and stability calculations for the urban barge, ensured stability under varying load conditions. The original design of existing barges in Ghent underwent revision and enhancement, taking into account simulations, tables, and statistics provided by stakeholders from various regions. With this objective, an optimized design for a new vessel was developed to enhance stability and seakeeping performance, resulting in a ship measuring 20 meters in length and 4.5 meters in width, offering enhanced transportation, economic efficiency, and sustainability benefits for inland stakeholders across Europe.

The development of the design for the new urban vessel involves collaboration across various components:

1. Study of the existing small urban vessel and the preparation of a simulation model by partner UGAL.
2. Analysis of the performance of the small urban vessel in shallow water through computer modeling of the vessel.
3. Investigation of extreme weather conditions in other inland waterway regions, enabling measurement of the effects of wind, currents, tides, and waves with the aim of optimizing the new barge design.
4. A comparative study has been carried out in connection with the various drivetrains for ships, inboard and outboard engines.
5. Research has been conducted into the various functionalities that the "Smart terminal" must have in order to be used flexibly and resiliently (loading ramp, drone, remote control equipment).
6. For the first scenario where a crane is placed on board, several scenarios were analysed, and some recommendations were made based on the weight of the loaded and unloaded cargo for an uncertain safe workload. Based on this, the design of the ship was adjusted, and the ro-ro mobile crane model was opted for, given the impact on the balance sheet.
7. This has resulted in the design of a new adapted ship based on the above data.

In Use case 3, ICCS integrates current sensor technologies into an IoT system to monitor and improve the resilience of Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) within the Digital Twin framework, specifically in support of Living Lab 1. Through this initiative, ICCS installs environmental sensors to enhance the physical infrastructure in Ghent, enabling better synchronization of water transport operations, especially during critical events such as low or high-water levels. The in-situ sensor network, supported by advanced sensing technologies and remote data transfer capabilities, enables accurate and timely water level monitoring, enhancing understanding of inland water dynamics and contributing to broader hydrological monitoring efforts in North-West Europe.

In Use case 4, the study comprises two main components:

- i) Utilizing batteries for urban vessel propulsion.
- ii) Utilizing vessel-installed batteries to transform the platform into a large-scale power supply infrastructure.

For propulsion, barges will utilize electric propulsion systems along with extended battery systems, either integrated within the barge or positioned on the deck. These batteries will offer an alternative power source for long-range propulsion.

The platform doubles as a substantial power supply, facilitating cascading effects during emergencies. The batteries serve as floating off-grid power suppliers, potentially supporting critical

facilities like hospitals or crisis centers. Collaborators include public grid network operators, private constructors in need of energy services, emergency units, and grid backup systems.

Initial testing has been completed, with further development planned over the next 12 months.

Regarding the application scenario, LL1 aims to enhance resilience and sustainability in inland waterway transport through the development of innovative solutions. Key scenarios to be addressed include:

- **Staff Loss Mitigation:** Developing automated procedures for terminal operations during staff loss scenarios caused by external calamities or pandemics. ITA will assess the effectiveness of automated systems in handling human-driven actions within specified timeframes, testing various degrees of personnel loss.
- **Infrastructure Resilience Assessment:** Evaluating the resilience of existing infrastructure and policymakers in creating emergency plans for disasters, particularly those related to climate change. This involves analysing planning lifespans, regional and policymaker preparedness, crisis center and rescue institution responses, and the presence of recovery and assistance programs.
- **Smart Terminal Operations Visualization:** IMEC's visualization of terminal operations, incorporating ship positions, environmental data, ramp size, and crane positions during loading and unloading, serves as a comprehensive tool for stakeholders. It can also facilitate the training of policymakers and rescue personnel.

Related to building of the new vessels stage, in M18, material purchases, including aluminium plates and engines, have been completed (for building the new urban barge). With the design finalized for the intended applications, hull welding and engine positioning are underway. The remaining applications and use cases outlined will be implemented in the upcoming months.

Assuming no unforeseen circumstances arise, and progress continues as planned, we anticipate completing the entire construction of the ship and the installation of propulsion and steering elements. Subsequently, an extensive testing period is scheduled, covering various elements such as the ship's behavior in shallow water and strong currents, remote-controlled sailing from the command center in Antwerp, and the setup of use cases to test the Floating Modular Platform (FMP) model in different configurations. Additionally, testing will be conducted on various components of the Smart Terminal, including the drone and remote-controlled crane.

5 Bibliography & Internet sources

5.1 Bibliography

1. Ambra, T., Caris, A., Macharis, C., 2018. Towards freight transport system unification: reviewing and combining the advancements in the physical internet and synchromodal transport research. *International Journal of Production Research* 57(6).
2. Al Enezy, O., van Hassel, E., Sys, C., Vanelslander, T., 2017. Developing a cost calculation model for inland navigation. *Res. Transp. Bus. Manag.* 23, 64–74.
3. Bellingmo, P.R., Wille, E., Nordahl, H., Mørkrid, O.E. and Holte, E.A., 2023. Analyzing the Feasibility of an Unmanned Cargo Ship for Different Operational Phases.
4. Bellingmo P.R. and Jørgensen U., 2022. Automatic Mooring: Technical Gap Analysis.
5. Christiansen, M., Fagerholt, K., Rachaniotis, N.P., Stålhane, M., 2017. Operational planning of routes and schedules for a fleet of fuel supply vessels. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 105, 163–175.
6. City Logistics, Challenges and Opportunities, Savelsbergh en van Woensel, February 2016
7. Corman, F., D’Ariano, A., Marra, A.D., Pacciarelli, D., Samà, M., 2017. Integrating train scheduling and delay management in real-time railway traffic control. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 105, 213–239.
8. Dong, C., Boute, R., McKinnon, A., Verelst, M., 2018. Investigating synchromodality from a supply chain perspective. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport Environment* 61,42–57.
9. Giusti, R., Manerba, D., Bruno, G., Tadei, R., 2019. Synchromodal logistics: An overview of critical success factors, enabling technologies, and open research issues. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 129, 92-110.
10. KennisDC Logistiek Gelderland; Binnenstaddistributie, “Het model Zutphen”, 2017
11. Koedijk, O. C. 2015. Paper 21-The role of classification and reference vessels in the design of inland fairways for commercial vessels – contribution to the Workshop of WG 141 Design Guidelines for Inland Waterways, "SMART RIVERS 2015", Buenos Aires, Argentina, 7-11 September 2015
12. Lee, C.Y., Lee, H.L., Zhang, J., 2015. The impact of slow ocean steaming on delivery reliability and fuel consumption. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 76, 176–190.
13. Li, L., Negenborn, R.R., De Schutter, B., 2017. Distributed model predictive control for cooperative synchromodal freight transport. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 105, 240–260.
14. Capgemini, 2016. Making the last mile pay.
15. Martinez-Pastor, 2018. Resilience of Traffic Networks to Extreme Weather Events: Analysis and Assessment

16. McKinsey&Company, Parcel Delivery, the future of last mile, September 2016
17. Outlook City Logistics, Topsector Logistiek, April 2017
18. Schipper en Roorda, Op zoek naar doorbraken in de stadslogistiek, September 2017
19. Schulte, F., Lalla-Ruiz, E., González-Ramírez, R.G., Voß, S., 2017. Reducing port-related empty truck emissions: a mathematical approach for truck appointments with collaboration. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 105, 195–212.
20. Swolfs, Sietze; Dekeyser, Nicolas; Haeseldonckx, Dries; Waeyenbergh, Geert; 2012. Characterization of a battery model using parameter estimation techniques. *Proceedings of the Electric Vehicle Symposium (EVS); 2012; Vol. 1; pp. 75 - 85*
21. Swolfs, Sietze; Vanierschot, Maarten; Slaets, Peter; Goethals, Pauwel; Denis, Kathleen; Haeseldonckx, Dries; 2013. Optimal integration of renewable energy sources into electric-vehicle charging infrastructure using linear programming. *3rd International Symposium on Engineering, Energy and Environment; 2013; pp. - Publisher: 3rd International Symposium on Engineering, Energy and Environment*
22. Tavasszy, L.A., Behdani, B., Konings, R., 2017. Intermodality and synchronomodality. In: Geerlings, H., Kuipers, B., Zuidwijk, R. (Eds.), *Ports and Networks – Strategies, Operations and Perspectives*. Routledge, London Chapter 16.
23. UPS & GreenBiz, *The Road to Sustainable Urban Logistics*, June 2017
24. Waeyenbergh, Geert; Dekeyser, Nicolas; Swolfs, Sietze; Ceuppens, Noesjka; Vermijlen, Tom; 2013. Stimulating Sustainable Innovation in Inland Waterway Navigation in Flanders - Pilot Project 'Ecorace-Challenge'. *Plugboat 2013 World Electric & Hybrid Boat Conference; 2013; Vol. 1; iss. 10; pp. 1 - 6*

5.2 Internet sources:

1. Brusselaers (2023), The impact of off-site construction transport on air quality, <https://researchportal.vub.be/en/publications/the-impact-of-off-site-construction-transport-on-airquality> CE Delft (2016),
2. https://ce.nl/wpcontent/uploads/2021/03/CE_Delft_4H63_De_omvang_van_stadslogistiek_Def.pdf
3. Circulatieplan, <https://stad.gent/nl/mobiliteit-openbare-werken/plannen-enrealisaties-mobiliteit/mobiliteitsplan-circulatieplan-en-parkeerplan-gent/circulatieplan-gent>
4. [Global Climate Highlights 2023 | Copernicus](#) Data from Copernicus are subject to the [License to Use Copernicus Products \(v 1.2\)](#). Datasets from other providers, which are included here, mainly for the purpose of comparison, are subject to other licences; please check with the respective provider.
5. C3S ERA5 1950–2022: [Data](#) | [Documentation](#)
6. EUMETSAT OSI SAF Sea Ice Index v2.2 [Data and Documentation](#)
7. C3S climate data record XCO₂ (2003-2022) [Data](#) | [Documentation](#)
8. C3S climate data record XCH₄ (2003-2022) [Data](#) | [Documentation](#)
9. GFAS V1.2 wildfire emissions [Data](#) | [Documentation](#)
10. CAMS near real-time data record XCO₂ V3.1 [Data and Documentation](#)
11. CAMS near real-time data record XCH₄ available at FTP: anonymous@ftp.sron.nl, directory: /pub/pub/RemoTeC/PROXY_NRT_L1X/
12. Mobiliteitsplan:

<https://stad.gent/nl/mobiliteit-openbare-werken/plannen-enrealisaties-mobiliteit/mobiliteitsplan-circulatieplan-en-parkeerplan-gent>

<https://stad.gent/nl/over-gent-stadsbestuur/over-gent/kaarten-cijfers-en-data/gentcijfers-en-kaart> ,

<https://open.innovatrix.be/public/apply/Open%20Innovatrix>,

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ghent><https://douro.apdl.pt/apex/f?p=100:1><https://www.ccr-zkr.org/>

<https://www.waterbouwkundiglaboratorium.be/en><https://zeroemissionservices.nl/en/homepage><https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Douro><https://www.inlandnavigation.eu/eu-topic/green-energy/>

https://www.inlandwaterwaytransport.eu/wp-content/uploads/Annual-Report-2021-final-draft_07032022.pdf

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/water-framework-directive-wfd-2000>

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/management/docs/iwt_en.pdf<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32001L0042>

<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/eudr/2007/60#:~:text=The%20purpose%20of%20this%20Directive,with%20floods%20in%20the%20Community.>

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/directive-2007-60-ec>
https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/catalog/envisat-gomos-level-2-atmospheric-constituents-profiles-gridded-user-friendly-product-gomos_ufp_gridded-

<https://ec.europa.eu/transport/about-us>

<http://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/st4w-smart-tracking-data-network-for-shipment-byinland-waterway>

13. UN Climate report: [WMO Provisional State of the Global Climate 2023.pdf](#)

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex 1

Annex 1 presents a detailed study of the recent climate changes and their impact on navigation conditions on inland waterways.

The past year 2023 was the warmest year since measurements began. This is reported by the **European Union's Earth observation program, Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)**. Explanations for the unusually high air temperatures could include rising concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere and the weather phenomena La Niña and El Niño.

In its climate report for the year 2023, C3S maps the climate extremes of the past year. Temperature data dating back to 1850 shows that 2023 was the hottest calendar year on record. The global average temperature last year was 14.98 degrees Celsius. That is 0.17 degrees Celsius warmer than in the previous record year 2016. Compared to the pre-industrial level from 1850 to 1900, it was 1.48 degrees Celsius warmer. "In 2023, the global average temperature rose more than we expected," the C3S scientists said.

See : [Global Climate Highlights 2023 | Copernicus](#)

KEY MESSAGES

- 2023 is confirmed as the warmest calendar year in global temperature data records going back to 1850
- 2023 had a global-average temperature of 14.98°C, 0.17°C higher than the previous highest annual value in 2016
- 2023 was 0.60°C warmer than the 1991-2020 average and 1.48°C warmer than the 1850-1900 pre-industrial level
- It is likely that a 12-month period ending in January or February 2024 will exceed 1.5°C above the pre-industrial level
- Each month from June to December in 2023 was warmer than the corresponding month in any previous year
- July and August 2023 were the warmest two months on record. Boreal summer (June-August) was also the warmest season on record
- In September 2023, the temperature deviation above the 1991-2020 average was larger than in any month in any year in the ERA5 dataset (0.93°C higher than the 1991-2020 average)
- October, November and December 2023, each with a temperature of 0.85°C above average, ranked all joint second-largest in terms of temperature deviation above the 1991-2020 average

For the first time in 2023, every day was at least one degree Celsius warmer than pre-industrial levels from 1850 to 1900. On almost half of the year's 365 days it was at least 1.5 degrees Celsius warmer. November 17 and 18 were the peaks in 2023 because it was even more than 2 degrees Celsius warmer: a first.

RECORD NUMBER OF DAYS ABOVE 1.5°C IN 2023

Number of days with temperature increase above pre-industrial level (1850-1900) within the following ranges:

■ 1 to 1.25°C
 ■ 1.25 to 1.5°C
 ■ 1.5°C or more

Data: ERA5 • Credit: C3S/ECMWF

PROGRAMME OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

Figure 44: Global Climate Highlights - Copernicus report 2023

From June to December, each month was warmer than the corresponding months of each previous year, the report further shows. July and August will go down in history as the hottest months ever recorded.

Figure 45: Global Climate Highlights - Copernicus report 2023

One explanation for the unusually high air temperatures is the unprecedentedly high surface temperatures in the ocean, the C3S explains. These are in turn caused by the continuously rising concentrations of greenhouse gases, which in 2023 reached the highest levels ever measured in the atmosphere. Compared to 2022, the level of carbon dioxide (CO₂) increased by 2.4 parts per million (ppm) to 419 ppm. The methane (CH₄) content increased by 11 parts per billion (ppb) to 1,920 ppb.

Another driving force behind the unprecedentedly high sea surface temperatures is a pattern called the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO). Under that pattern, temperatures in the central and eastern Pacific Ocean fluctuate between cooler (La Niña) and warmer (El Niño) conditions than average. This affects temperatures and weather around the world. La Niña came to an end in early 2023. The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) declared that El Niño started in July. But even without El Niño, 2023 would have been an exceptional year, Burgess emphasizes. “After all, record temperatures have been measured in the ocean since April, long before El Niño started.”

And also, outside the central and eastern Pacific Ocean, high sea surface temperatures contributed to the records in 2023: marine heat waves occurred in the Mediterranean Sea, the Gulf of Mexico and the Caribbean Sea, the Indian Ocean and the northern part of the Pacific Ocean, and the North Atlantic Ocean.

2023 has replaced 2016 as the warmest calendar year on record. According to the ERA5 dataset, the global-average temperature for 2023 was 14.98°C, 0.17°C higher than recorded for 2016.

Figure 46: Global Climate Highlights - Copernicus report 2023

In the report is mentioned that [Extreme events around the world in 2023](#) had significant impacts on human health, ecosystems, nature and infrastructure. Among the most exceptional were flooding, wildfires, drought, and extreme heat.

Impactful flooding events ranged from flash floods caused by intense rainfall to large-scale flooding due to the passage of atmospheric rivers (such as in California in January and March, and over Chile in July), monsoon rainfall, large low-pressure systems, and tropical cyclones. Cyclone Freddy impacted southeast Africa (February, March), Cyclone Mocha south and southeast Asia (May), Hurricane Hilary Mexico and the western USA (August), Hurricane Otis Mexico, (October), Storm Daniel the Mediterranean (September), and post-tropical cyclone Jasper Australia, (December), among others. In some cases, such as in the Horn of Africa during Autumn, flooding may have been exacerbated by particularly low soil moisture levels that favoured and accelerated runoff.

Many other regions across the globe suffered from prolonged lack of precipitation, in North (Mexico) and South America (Amazon basin, Pantanal wetlands, Argentina, Uruguay) and western Africa. Heatwaves occurred around the world during 2023, often breaking national or local temperature records. Significant occurrences in southern Europe, North Africa, and parts of North America and Asia, were followed in seasonal progression by occurrences over parts of South America, southern Africa and Australia.

Hot and dry conditions in some regions also contributed to extensive wildfires, notably in southern Europe, Canada (in particular the Northwest Territories, and with significant contribution to [global carbon emissions](#)), South America, Australia and Hawaii, among others.

Europe: high variability and many extreme events

2023 was the second-warmest year for Europe, at 1.02°C above the 1991-2020 average, 0.17°C cooler than 2020, the warmest year on record.

Temperatures in Europe were above average for 11 months during 2023 and September was the warmest September on record.

European winter (December 2022 – February 2023) was the second-warmest winter on record.

The average temperature for the European summer (June-August) was 19.63°C; at 0.83°C above average, it was the fifth warmest on record. During the season, Europe experienced heatwaves, including marine heatwaves, with multiple daily temperature records broken and widespread drier-than-average conditions on land.

European autumn (September-November) had an average temperature of 10.96°C, which is 1.43°C above average. This made autumn the second warmest on record, just 0.03°C cooler than autumn 2020.

Heavy precipitation triggered significant flood events across the continent, from spring onwards. Europe experienced considerable storms and flooding. Significant flood events triggered by heavy, or record-breaking precipitation, occurred in Emilia-Romagna, Italy, in May; in Norway and Sweden (storm Hans) and Slovenia in August. In autumn, there were multiple storms and associated flooding including: in Greece in September (Storm Daniel, also behind devastating flooding in Libya); in October in northern and western Europe (Storm Babet); across the Iberian Peninsula (storm Aline); and across most of western Europe (Storm Ciarán). Further storms affected central (Storm Ciro) and northwestern Europe (Storms Elin, Fergus, Pia, Gerrit and Geraldine) in December.

In Europe, events such as the last flooding in Germany in 2016, in France in 2016 - 2020, and in Belgium in 2021 are increasingly often creating threatening scenarios. Between 1998 and 2004 in Europe, floods caused some 700 fatalities, the displacement of about half a million people and at least EUR 25 billion in insured economic losses, (European-Commission (2004)).

In addition, these situations occur not only more frequently but also reaching levels that were not previously foreseen. These kinds of perturbations often cause significant losses, which can last prolonged period, from the moment when the perturbation starts until the total recovery.

See in that item also the action taken by the European Commission: [Recommendation for 2040 emissions reduction target \(europa.eu\)](#)

6.2 Annex 2

Annex 2 provides data and statistics related to meteorological, hydrological, and port operations within the Hamburg Port Area. Information of the reference area with strong current, strong wind, and high waves.

 AM Gewässerkunde Hr. Heyenga, 42847-2405 Hydrologie Hr. Strotmann, 42847-2801		Pegel Hamburg-St.Pauli 	
Gewässerkundliche Information 2024 Gewässerkundliches Jahr 2023 (01.11.2022 - 31.10.2023)			
Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2019 - 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 3,94 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,87 m (19.02.22)	NHN + 5,48 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,44 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,44 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,07 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,54 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,68 m (17.02.22)	NHN + 1,39 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 3,50 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 3,50 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 3,64 m (18.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,17 m	NHN + 2,15 m	NHN + 2,15 m *)
MTnw	NHN - 1,66 m	NHN - 1,67 m	NHN - 1,66 m *)
MThb	3,83 m	3,82 m	3,81 m
MHW	NHN + 2,13 m	Vom BSH festgelegt für das Kalenderjahr 2024	
MINW	NHN - 1,70 m		
MTH	3,83 m		
Extremwerte Stand: 01.11.2023			
Thw (seit 1788)		Tnw (seit 1901)	
1.	NHN + 6,45 m (03.01.1976) = HHThw	1.	NHN - 3,64 m (18.03.2018) = NNTnw
2.	+ 6,08 m (06.12.2013)	2.	- 3,50 m (20.10.2023)
3.	+ 6,02 m (28.01.1994)	3.	- 3,48 m (02.03.1987)
4.	+ 6,02 m (10.01.1995)	4.	- 3,48 m (21.10.2023)
5.	+ 5,95 m (03.12.1999)	5.	- 3,46 m (01.03.2018)
6.	+ 5,87 m (19.02.2022)	6.	- 3,45 m (18.12.1997)
7.	+ 5,81 m (24.11.1981)	7.	- 3,41 m (18.03.2018)
8.	+ 5,76 m (23.01.1993)	8.	- 3,39 m (07.02.2021)
9.	+ 5,75 m (28.02.1990)	9.	- 3,38 m (15.02.1994)
10.	+ 5,74 m (05.02.1999)	10.	- 3,38 m (01.03.2018)
Dauerzahlen Mittelwerte aus den Jahresreihen 2004-2023 (Thw) bzw. 2014-2023 (Tnw)			
Bei 706 Tiden/Jahr wurden bei Thw überschritten		Bei 706 Tiden/Jahr wurden bei Tnw unterschritten	
NHN + 4,00 m	2,7 - mal	NHN - 1,60 m	459,8 - mal
NHN + 3,00 m	24,2 - mal	NHN - 2,00 m	125,1 - mal
NHN + 2,20 m	279,0 - mal	NHN - 2,40 m	14,6 - mal
		Detaillierte Angaben siehe Anlage 3	
Oberwasserzufluss am Pegel Neu Darchau in m³/s (6 Uhr-Terminwerte; tw. ungeprüfte Rohwerte)			
	Jahresreihe 2023	98 - Jahresreihe 1926 - 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2019 - 2023
NQ	188 (25.07.2023) #	145 (02.10.1947)	160 (08.09.2019) #
MQ	488	691	460
HQ	1290 (22.03.2023)	4050 (11.06.2013)	1320 (14.02.2021)

AM Gewässerkunde
Hr. Heyenga, 42847-2405
Hydrologie
Hr. Strotmann, 42847-2801

Gewässerkundliche Information 2024
Gewässerkundliches Jahr 2023
(01.11.2022 - 31.10.2023)

Pegel im Hafengebiet

Pegel Hamburg - St. Pauli

Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 3,94 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,48 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,44 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,07 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,54 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,39 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 3,50 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 3,64 m (18.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,17 m	NHN + 2,15 m*) Siehe NHN - 1,66 m*) Fußnote
MTnw	NHN - 1,66 m	
MThb	3,83 m	3,81 m

Pegel Hamburg - Harburg

Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 3,98 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,53 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,43 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,06 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,51 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,39 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 3,42 m (21.10.23)	NHN - 3,41 m (18.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,20 m	NHN + 2,20 m
MTnw	NHN - 1,67 m	NHN - 1,67 m
MThb	3,87 m	3,87 m

Pegel Seemannshöft

Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 3,88 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,40 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,48 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,10 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,54 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,43 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 3,45 m (21.10.23)	NHN - 3,55 m (17.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,11 m	NHN + 2,08 m
MTnw	NHN - 1,61 m	NHN - 1,62 m
MThb	3,72 m	3,70 m

Pegel U.F. Blankenese

Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 3,81 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,35 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,52 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,11 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,54 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,46 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 3,41 m (21.10.23)	NHN - 3,49 m (17.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,03 m	NHN + 2,02 m
MTnw	NHN - 1,57 m	NHN - 1,55 m
MThb	3,60 m	3,57 m

Pegel Bunthaus

Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 4,03 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,51 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,36 m (20.10.23)	NHN + 0,03 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,59 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,43 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 2,80 m (21.10.23)	NHN - 2,58 m (18.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,29 m	NHN + 2,27 m
MTnw	NHN - 1,29 m	NHN - 1,31 m
MThb	3,58 m	3,58 m

Pegel Schöpfstelle

Hauptwerte	Jahresreihe 2023	5 - Jahresreihe 2016 - 2020
HThw	NHN + 3,98 m (14.10.23)	NHN + 5,54 m (29.10.17)
NThw	NHN - 0,42 m (20.10.23)	NHN - 0,01 m (03.01.16)
HTnw	NHN + 0,52 m (30.01.23)	NHN + 1,42 m (26.12.16)
NTnw	NHN - 3,23 m (21.10.23)	NHN - 3,19 m (18.03.18)
MThw	NHN + 2,22 m	NHN + 2,21 m
MTnw	NHN - 1,59 m	NHN - 1,60 m
MThb	3,81 m	3,81 m

Begriffe aus der Gewässerkunde

Bezeichnung	Definition												
NHN = Normalhöhennull	Ämtlich festgelegte Bezugsebene für Höhenmessungen in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland. Für die gewässerkundlichen Daten der HPA erfolgte die Umstellung vom Deutschen Haupthöhennetz 1992 (DHHN92) auf das neue DHHN2016 am 01.11.2019. Alle Höhenangaben in der vorliegenden Gewässerkundlichen Information ab den 01.11.2019 sowie die Mittelwerte der 5-Jahresreihen beziehen sich auf das DHHN2016. Frühere Wasserstandsdaten beziehen sich auf die zum jeweiligen Zeitpunkt gültige Bezugsebene.												
SKN = Seekartennull	Ämtlich festgelegte Bezugsebene für Tiefenmessungen auf See und in Tidenströmen. Das Seekartennull im Seegebiet vor der deutschen Nordseeküste einschließlich der Watten und Ästuare ist gleich dem örtlich niedrigstmöglichen Gezeitenwasserstand (Lowest Astronomical Tide, LAT). Im Tidebereich der Ems, Jade, Weser und Elbe ist das Seekartennull in Anlehnung an den niedrigstmöglichen Gezeitenwasserstand unter Berücksichtigung des Oberwassereinflusses stufenweise festgelegt. Das Seekartennull (SKN) wird seit dem 01.11.2023 auf den aktuellen Bezugshorizont (DHHN2016) bezogen. Das SKN liegt (analog zu den PNP) in Hamburg zwischen NHN-1,904 m (Pegel St. Pauli) und NHN-1,928 m (Pegel Blankenese und Schöpfstelle).												
KN = Kartennull	Parallel zum Seekartennull (SKN) gibt es im Bereich des Hamburger Hafens das Kartennull (KN), das sich an der Höhe des mittleren Tideniedrigwassers (MTnw) orientiert. Seit dem 01.05.2016 ist das KN in Hamburg mit NHN -1,60 m festgesetzt.												
PNP = Pegelnullpunkt (früher PN = Pegelnull)	Höhenlage des Nullpunktes eines Pegels bezogen auf Normalhöhennull. Für die Hamburger Pegel ergeben sich durch die Einführung des DHHN2016 ab dem 01.11.2019 folgende Pegelnullpunkte: <table border="0" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr> <td>St. Pauli</td> <td>-500,4 cm NHN (DHHN2016)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Harburg</td> <td>-501,5 cm NHN (")</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Seemannshöft</td> <td>-501,7 cm NHN (")</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UF Blankenese</td> <td>-501,8 cm NHN (")</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Schöpfstelle</td> <td>-501,8 cm NHN (")</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Bunthaus</td> <td>-501,7 cm NHN (")</td> </tr> </table>	St. Pauli	-500,4 cm NHN (DHHN2016)	Harburg	-501,5 cm NHN (")	Seemannshöft	-501,7 cm NHN (")	UF Blankenese	-501,8 cm NHN (")	Schöpfstelle	-501,8 cm NHN (")	Bunthaus	-501,7 cm NHN (")
St. Pauli	-500,4 cm NHN (DHHN2016)												
Harburg	-501,5 cm NHN (")												
Seemannshöft	-501,7 cm NHN (")												
UF Blankenese	-501,8 cm NHN (")												
Schöpfstelle	-501,8 cm NHN (")												
Bunthaus	-501,7 cm NHN (")												
Thw = Tidehochwasser	Höchster Wert der Tidekurve zwischen zwei aufeinanderfolgenden Tnw.												
Tnw = Tideniedrigwasser	Niedrigster Wert der Tidekurve zwischen zwei aufeinanderfolgenden Thw.												
Thb = Tidehub	Mittlerer Höhenunterschied zwischen Thw und den beiden benachbarten Tnw.												
MThb = Mittlerer Tidehub	Arithmetischer Mittelwert der Tidehöhe eines bestimmten betrachteten Zeitraums.												
HHThw	Höchstes bekanntes Tidehochwasser.												
HThw / HTnw	Höchster Wert des Tidehoch- bzw. Tideniedrigwassers eines bestimmten betrachteten Zeitraums.												
MThw / MTnw	Arithmetischer Mittelwert der Tidehochwasserstände bzw. Tideniedrigwasserstände eines bestimmten betrachteten Zeitraums.												
NThw / NTnw	Niedrigster Wert des Tidehoch- bzw. Tideniedrigwassers eines bestimmten betrachteten Zeitraums.												
NNTnw	Niedrigstes bekanntes Tideniedrigwasser.												
Tmw = Tidemittelwasser	Wasserstand der waagerechten Schwerelinie einer Tidekurve. Das mittlere Tidemittelwasser (MTmw) entspricht dem sog. MSL (Mean Sea Level). Am Pegel St. Pauli beträgt das MTmw (2016-2020) NHN +0,37 m.												
MHW = Mittleres Hochwasser MNW = Mittleres Niedrigwasser MTH = Mittlerer Tidehub	Gezeitengrundwerte, die vom Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie (BSH) nach einem speziellen Analyseverfahren aus in der Regel fünf Beobachtungsjahren von weitgehend windunbeeinflussten Tidehochwasserständen bzw. Tideniedrigwasserständen ermittelt werden. MHW und MNW sind die Bezugshöhen für Wasserstandsvorhersagen des BSH.												
6 Uhr-Terminwert (beim Oberwasserzufluss)	Täglich um 6 Uhr bestimmte Höhe des Oberwasserzuflusses an einer Messstelle.												

Mittlere jährliche Über- und Unterschreitungshäufigkeiten von Wasserständen

Pegel Hamburg - St. Pauli

Thw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Überschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
2,20	279,0	39,53%
2,40	146,4	20,74%
2,60	76,5	10,83%
2,80	41,6	5,80%
3,00	24,2	3,42%
3,20	14,2	2,00%
3,40	9,5	1,34%
3,60	6,4	0,91%
3,80	3,9	0,55%
4,00	2,7	0,38%
4,20	1,7	0,23%

Datengrundlage: 2004 - 2023 (20 Jahre)

Pegel Hamburg - Harburg

Thw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Überschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
2,20	330,4	46,82%
2,40	183,1	25,94%
2,60	96,6	13,69%
2,80	51,4	7,28%
3,00	29,5	4,17%
3,20	16,6	2,35%
3,40	10,7	1,52%
3,60	7,6	1,08%
3,80	4,8	0,67%
4,00	3,1	0,43%
4,20	1,9	0,27%

Datengrundlage: 2004 - 2023 (20 Jahre)

Tnw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Unterschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
-1,60	459,8	65,16%
-1,70	375,4	53,20%
-1,80	288,7	40,92%
-1,90	196,2	27,81%
-2,00	125,1	17,73%
-2,10	71,3	10,10%
-2,20	41,9	5,94%
-2,30	23,4	3,32%
-2,40	14,6	2,07%
-2,50	9,6	1,36%
-2,60	6,1	0,86%

Datengrundlage: 2014 - 2023 (10 Jahre)

Tnw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Unterschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
-1,60	454,3	64,38%
-1,70	369,8	52,41%
-1,80	279,4	39,60%
-1,90	185,9	26,35%
-2,00	113,8	16,13%
-2,10	62,6	8,87%
-2,20	35,3	5,00%
-2,30	19,7	2,79%
-2,40	11,4	1,62%
-2,50	7,7	1,09%
-2,60	5,2	0,74%

Datengrundlage: 2014 - 2023 (10 Jahre)

Pegel Seemannshöft

Thw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Überschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
2,20	342,6	34,37%
2,40	122,8	12,40%
2,60	63,7	6,38%
2,80	35,6	3,56%
3,00	20,3	2,03%
3,20	12,4	1,24%
3,40	8,5	0,85%
3,60	5,6	0,56%
3,80	3,4	0,34%
4,00	2,1	0,21%
4,20	1,4	0,14%

Datengrundlage: 2004 - 2023 (20 Jahre)

Pegel U.F. Blankenese

Thw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Überschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
2,20	197,8	28,03%
2,40	101,3	14,35%
2,60	52,5	7,43%
2,80	30,2	4,28%
3,00	16,8	2,37%
3,20	10,9	1,54%
3,40	7,5	1,05%
3,60	4,6	0,65%
3,80	3,1	0,44%
4,00	2,0	0,28%
4,20	1,2	0,17%

Datengrundlage: 2004 - 2023 (20 Jahre)

Tnw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Unterschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
-1,60	395,3	56,02%
-1,70	309,0	43,79%
-1,80	217,5	30,82%
-1,90	139,9	19,83%
-2,00	80,4	11,39%
-2,10	46,8	6,63%
-2,20	26,2	3,71%
-2,30	15,9	2,25%
-2,40	10,2	1,45%
-2,50	6,6	0,94%
-2,60	4,8	0,68%

Datengrundlage: 2014 - 2023 (10 Jahre)

Tnw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Unterschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
-1,60	353,0	50,03%
-1,70	261,4	37,05%
-1,80	174,3	24,70%
-1,90	106,6	15,11%
-2,00	62,0	8,79%
-2,10	35,8	5,07%
-2,20	20,1	2,85%
-2,30	11,5	1,63%
-2,40	8,5	1,20%
-2,50	5,8	0,82%
-2,60	3,9	0,55%

Datengrundlage: 2014 - 2023 (10 Jahre)

Pegel Bunthaus

Thw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Überschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
2,20	407,4	57,73%
2,40	248,2	35,17%
2,60	132,1	18,72%
2,80	69,9	9,90%
3,00	39,2	5,55%
3,20	22,5	3,18%
3,40	13,6	1,93%
3,60	8,8	1,25%
3,80	6,1	0,86%
4,00	3,8	0,54%
4,20	2,5	0,35%

Datengrundlage: 2004 - 2023 (20 Jahre)

Pegel Schöpfstelle

Thw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Überschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
2,20	345,1	48,89%
2,40	195,1	27,64%
2,60	103,1	14,60%
2,80	54,0	7,65%
3,00	31,2	4,41%
3,20	17,4	2,47%
3,40	11,1	1,57%
3,60	7,5	1,06%
3,80	4,8	0,68%
4,00	3,2	0,45%
4,20	1,9	0,27%

Datengrundlage: 2004 - 2023 (20 Jahre)

Tnw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Unterschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
-1,60	105,2	14,91%
-1,70	51,1	7,24%
-1,80	23,4	3,32%
-1,90	12,0	1,70%
-2,00	7,8	1,11%
-2,10	5,0	0,71%
-2,20	2,5	0,35%
-2,30	1,5	0,21%
-2,40	1,3	0,18%
-2,50	0,5	0,07%
-2,60	0,3	0,04%

Datengrundlage: 2014 - 2023 (10 Jahre)

Tnw Wasserstand (m NHN)	Anzahl Unterschreitungen pro Jahr	Häufigkeit (%)
-1,60	386,0	54,71%
-1,70	291,1	41,26%
-1,80	192,3	27,25%
-1,90	114,8	16,27%
-2,00	60,8	8,62%
-2,10	33,9	4,80%
-2,20	18,5	2,62%
-2,30	10,1	1,43%
-2,40	7,1	1,01%
-2,50	5,0	0,71%
-2,60	3,0	0,43%

Datengrundlage: 2014 - 2023 (10 Jahre)

Angaben zu den Eintrittshäufigkeiten noch höherer bzw. niedriger Wasserstände sollten nur auf Grundlage gesonderter langzeitstatistischer Auswertungen unter Einbeziehung historischer Daten gemacht werden.
Bitte wenden Sie sich bei Bedarf an hydrologie@hpa-hamburg.de.

Eine lineare Extrapolation und Interpolation der Tabellenwerte ist nicht sinnvoll.

Anzahl Sturmfluten am Pegel St. Pauli seit 1951

6.3 Annex 3

Annex 3 presents detailed results of the hydrostatic calculations conducted for different options of the maximum length of the newly designed vessel.

Table A3.1: Hydrostatics – LOA 20 meters

Draft Amidships m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Displacement t	0.2875	1.087	2.315	3.843	5.666	7.795	10.25	13.05	16.16	19.48	22.98	26.52	30.09	33.69	37.32	40.98
Heel deg	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Draft at FP m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Draft at AP m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Draft at LCF m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Trim (+ve by stern) m	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
WL Length m	16.115	16.778	17.105	17.334	17.506	17.639	17.737	17.816	18.499	19.215	19.342	19.387	19.431	19.469	19.504	19.540
Beam max extents on WL m	0.837	1.683	2.142	2.502	2.859	3.221	3.582	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900
Wetted Area m ²	11.261	21.014	28.270	34.565	40.733	47.362	54.406	61.444	67.211	72.893	76.561	78.892	81.811	83.435	85.641	87.838
Waterpl. Area m ²	11.048	20.285	26.950	32.728	38.424	44.615	51.256	58.008	62.686	66.953	68.717	69.398	70.010	70.564	71.038	71.501
Prismatic coeff. (Cp)	0.849	0.759	0.731	0.730	0.734	0.741	0.751	0.762	0.752	0.745	0.761	0.777	0.790	0.801	0.811	0.819
Block coeff. (Cb)	0.416	0.376	0.411	0.432	0.442	0.446	0.450	0.458	0.486	0.507	0.540	0.570	0.596	0.619	0.638	0.656
Max Sect. area coeff. (Cm)	0.499	0.502	0.567	0.597	0.606	0.607	0.601	0.602	0.646	0.682	0.711	0.735	0.755	0.773	0.788	0.801
Waterpl. area coeff. (Cwp)	0.819	0.719	0.736	0.754	0.768	0.785	0.807	0.835	0.869	0.894	0.911	0.918	0.924	0.929	0.934	0.938
LCB from zero pt. (+ve fwd) m	9.232	9.842	10.088	10.168	10.177	10.143	10.072	9.974	9.855	9.724	9.594	9.507	9.449	9.411	9.385	9.369
LCF from zero pt. (+ve fwd) m	9.597	10.261	10.314	10.241	10.147	9.964	9.727	9.498	9.247	8.931	8.899	8.980	9.053	9.120	9.177	9.233
KB m	0.033	0.066	0.098	0.129	0.160	0.192	0.224	0.256	0.289	0.321	0.352	0.382	0.411	0.439	0.467	0.494
KG m	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800
BMt m	1.923	3.621	3.812	3.863	4.026	4.274	4.584	4.900	4.528	4.122	3.637	3.201	2.860	2.586	2.358	2.170
BML m	635.458	273.796	177.248	137.473	115.196	103.976	97.819	93.000	90.233	89.672	81.580	72.487	65.334	59.563	54.748	50.738
GMt m	1.156	2.887	3.109	3.192	3.386	3.666	4.008	4.357	4.017	3.642	3.189	2.782	2.471	2.225	2.025	1.864
GML m	634.691	273.062	176.546	136.802	114.556	103.367	97.242	92.456	89.722	89.192	81.131	72.068	64.945	59.202	54.415	50.433
KMt m	1.956	3.687	3.909	3.992	4.186	4.466	4.808	5.157	4.817	4.442	3.989	3.582	3.271	3.025	2.825	2.664

Draft Amidships m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
KML m	635.491	273.862	177.346	137.602	115.356	104.167	98.042	93.256	90.522	89.992	81.931	72.868	65.745	60.002	55.215	51.233
Immersion (TPc) tonne/cm	0.113	0.208	0.276	0.335	0.394	0.457	0.525	0.595	0.643	0.686	0.704	0.711	0.718	0.723	0.728	0.733
MTc tonne.m	0.093	0.152	0.209	0.269	0.332	0.412	0.510	0.617	0.742	0.889	0.954	0.978	1.000	1.021	1.039	1.058
RM at 1deg = GMt.Disp.si n(1) tonne.m	0.006	0.055	0.126	0.214	0.335	0.499	0.717	0.992	1.133	1.238	1.279	1.288	1.298	1.309	1.319	1.333
Max deck inclination deg	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Trim angle (+ve by stern) deg	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Table A3.2: Hydrostatics, LOA 25 meters

Draft Amidships m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Displacement t	0.3915	1.513	3.239	5.358	7.866	10.77	14.08	17.82	21.92	26.24	30.74	35.27	39.84	44.44	49.07	53.72
Heel deg	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Draft at Fp m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Draft at Ap m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Draft at LCF m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
Trim (+ve by stern) m	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
WL Length m	21.115	21.778	22.105	22.334	22.506	22.639	22.737	22.816	23.499	24.215	24.342	24.387	24.431	24.469	24.504	24.540
Beam max extents on WL m	0.836	1.685	2.141	2.500	2.859	3.220	3.580	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900
Wetted Area m^2	15.435	29.481	38.962	47.158	55.446	63.782	72.278	80.990	87.662	93.827	97.914	100.733	103.534	106.265	108.994	111.670
Waterpl. Area m^2	15.191	28.692	37.513	45.132	52.874	60.690	68.698	77.051	82.374	86.474	88.151	88.836	89.468	89.987	90.499	90.918
Prismatic coeff. (Cp)	0.885	0.813	0.790	0.789	0.792	0.798	0.804	0.812	0.803	0.796	0.808	0.821	0.831	0.840	0.848	0.855
Block coeff. (Cb)	0.433	0.402	0.445	0.468	0.477	0.480	0.482	0.488	0.519	0.542	0.574	0.603	0.628	0.649	0.668	0.685
Max Sect. area coeff. (Cm)	0.500	0.500	0.568	0.597	0.608	0.605	0.602	0.603	0.647	0.682	0.711	0.735	0.756	0.773	0.788	0.802
Waterpl. area coeff. (Cwp)	0.861	0.782	0.793	0.808	0.822	0.833	0.844	0.866	0.899	0.916	0.929	0.934	0.939	0.943	0.947	0.950
LCB from zero pt.	11.747	12.370	12.606	12.678	12.679	12.637	12.566	12.466	12.349	12.221	12.096	12.012	11.955	11.917	11.891	11.876

Draft Amidships m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800
(+ve fwd) m																
LCF from zero pt. (+ve fwd) m	12.114	12.775	12.835	12.741	12.585	12.415	12.218	11.984	11.705	11.416	11.395	11.477	11.553	11.617	11.680	11.732
KB m	0.033	0.066	0.098	0.129	0.160	0.191	0.223	0.255	0.287	0.318	0.348	0.377	0.406	0.434	0.461	0.488
KG m	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800
BMt m	2.038	3.947	4.003	3.991	4.154	4.381	4.643	4.931	4.493	4.025	3.538	3.121	2.795	2.527	2.310	2.123
BML m	1165.032	514.044	324.347	247.927	208.146	183.097	166.387	155.324	147.774	141.456	127.391	113.275	102.191	93.081	85.612	79.219
GMt m	1.271	3.213	3.301	3.320	3.513	3.772	4.066	4.386	3.979	3.542	3.086	2.699	2.401	2.161	1.971	1.812
GML m	1164.265	513.310	323.645	247.256	207.506	182.488	165.809	154.778	147.261	140.974	126.939	112.853	101.797	92.715	85.273	78.907
KMt m	2.071	4.013	4.101	4.120	4.313	4.572	4.866	5.186	4.779	4.342	3.886	3.499	3.201	2.961	2.771	2.612
KML m	1165.065	514.110	324.445	248.056	208.306	183.288	166.609	155.578	148.061	141.774	127.739	113.653	102.597	93.515	86.073	79.707
Immersion (TPc) tonne/cm	0.156	0.294	0.385	0.463	0.542	0.622	0.704	0.790	0.844	0.886	0.904	0.911	0.917	0.922	0.928	0.932
MTc tonne.m	0.186	0.316	0.427	0.540	0.665	0.801	0.951	1.124	1.315	1.508	1.590	1.622	1.653	1.679	1.705	1.727
RM at 1deg = GMt.Disp.s in(1) tonne.m	0.009	0.085	0.187	0.310	0.482	0.709	0.999	1.364	1.522	1.622	1.656	1.661	1.669	1.676	1.688	1.698
Max deck inclination deg	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Trim angle (+ve by stern) deg	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Table A3.3: Hydrostatics, LOA 30 meters

Draft Amidships m	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	0.8	0.85	0.9	0.95	1.0	1.05
Displacement t	0.4951	1.938	4.164	6.877	10.07	13.74	17.91	22.59	27.69	33.01	38.50	44.03	49.60	55.20	60.82	66.47	72.13	77.82	83.53	89.26	95.00
Heel deg	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Draft at FP m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800	0.850	0.900	0.950	1.000	1.050
Draft at AP m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800	0.850	0.900	0.950	1.000	1.050
Draft at LCF m	0.050	0.100	0.150	0.200	0.250	0.300	0.350	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600	0.650	0.700	0.750	0.800	0.850	0.900	0.950	1.000	1.050
Trim (+ve by stern) m	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
WL Length m	26.115	26.778	27.105	27.334	27.506	27.639	27.737	27.816	28.499	29.215	29.342	29.387	29.431	29.469	29.504	29.540	29.575	29.610	29.646	29.681	29.716

Draft Amidships m	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	0.8	0.85	0.9	0.95	1.0	1.05	
Beam max extents on WL m	0.834	1.685	2.138	2.502	2.859	3.221	3.581	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900	3.900
Wetted Area m ²	19.594	37.893	49.820	59.844	69.841	79.906	90.037	101.041	107.087	114.080	119.055	122.037	125.020	128.009	132.008	135.002	138.004	141.008	144.008	147.009	151.027	151.027
Waterpl. Area m ²	19.343	37.090	48.329	57.728	67.121	76.617	86.334	96.649	101.735	105.962	107.609	108.277	108.908	109.436	109.956	110.369	110.791	111.163	111.565	111.986	112.424	112.874
Prismatic coeff. (Cp)	0.901	0.847	0.829	0.827	0.830	0.835	0.839	0.844	0.836	0.830	0.840	0.851	0.859	0.867	0.873	0.879	0.883	0.888	0.892	0.895	0.898	0.898
Block coeff. (Cb)	0.444	0.419	0.407	0.409	0.400	0.402	0.403	0.408	0.404	0.405	0.409	0.425	0.449	0.469	0.488	0.504	0.518	0.531	0.542	0.552	0.562	0.572
Max Sect. area coeff. (Cm)	0.503	0.500	0.506	0.509	0.508	0.503	0.501	0.502	0.506	0.508	0.511	0.507	0.505	0.507	0.507	0.508	0.508	0.508	0.508	0.508	0.508	0.508
Waterpl. area coeff. (Cwp)	0.888	0.822	0.834	0.844	0.853	0.861	0.869	0.891	0.915	0.930	0.940	0.945	0.949	0.952	0.956	0.958	0.961	0.963	0.965	0.967	0.967	0.970
LCB from zero pt. (+ve fwd) m	14.278	14.897	15.120	15.184	15.181	15.136	15.061	14.959	14.844	14.718	14.595	14.513	14.457	14.419	14.395	14.379	14.369	14.365	14.364	14.367	14.372	14.372
LCF from zero pt. (+ve fwd) m	14.635	15.292	15.305	15.208	15.068	14.895	14.685	14.407	14.208	13.901	13.894	13.976	14.052	14.117	14.181	14.232	14.284	14.330	14.380	14.420	14.479	14.479
KB m	0.034	0.066	0.098	0.129	0.159	0.191	0.222	0.254	0.285	0.316	0.346	0.375	0.403	0.430	0.458	0.485	0.511	0.538	0.564	0.591	0.617	0.643
KG m	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.800
BMt m	2.112	4.129	4.120	4.088	4.224	4.434	4.681	4.954	4.467	3.965	3.482	3.073	2.753	2.491	2.278	2.095	1.942	1.809	1.695	1.592	1.507	1.437
BML m	1863.328	837.159	526.081	396.143	326.868	284.096	255.917	238.168	218.355	205.460	183.916	163.550	147.503	134.345	123.526	114.245	106.408	99.577	93.726	88.442	84.098	84.098
GMt m	1.346	3.395	3.418	3.416	3.584	3.824	4.103	4.407	3.953	3.481	3.027	2.647	2.356	2.122	1.936	1.780	1.653	1.547	1.459	1.383	1.324	1.274
GML m	1862.562	836.425	525.379	395.471	326.228	283.487	255.339	238.137	217.600	204.976	183.461	163.124	147.104	133.975	123.183	113.930	106.111	99.315	93.490	88.233	83.915	83.915
KMt m	2.146	4.195	4.218	4.216	4.384	4.624	4.903	5.207	4.753	4.281	3.827	3.447	3.156	2.922	2.736	2.580	2.453	2.347	2.259	2.183	2.124	2.074
KML m	1863.362	837.225	526.179	396.271	327.028	284.287	256.139	238.937	218.400	205.776	184.261	163.924	147.904	134.775	123.983	114.730	106.919	100.115	94.290	89.033	84.715	84.715
Immersi on (TPc)	0.198	0.380	0.495	0.592	0.688	0.785	0.885	0.991	1.043	1.086	1.103	1.111	1.116	1.119	1.121	1.123	1.125	1.127	1.129	1.131	1.133	1.135

Draft Amidships m	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	0.8	0.85	0.9	0.95	1.0	1.05	
tonne/cm																						
MTc tonne.m	0.312	0.549	0.741	0.921	1.112	1.319	1.548	1.821	2.040	2.291	2.391	2.432	2.470	2.503	2.536	2.564	2.591	2.616	2.644	2.666	2.699	2.726
RM at 1deg = GMT.Disp.sin(1) tonne.m	0.012	0.115	0.248	0.410	0.630	0.917	1.283	1.738	1.910	2.006	2.034	2.034	2.039	2.044	2.055	2.065	2.081	2.101	2.127	2.154	2.195	2.249
Max deck inclination deg	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Trim angle (+ve by stern) deg	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000